

D4.5 Policy Recommendations

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Abstract

This deliverable presents the COcyber policy recommendations for strengthening civilian–defence cybersecurity coordination in Europe. It addresses the growing interdependence between civilian infrastructures, defence preparedness, public authorities, private operators, research actors and critical digital supply chains in a threat environment where cyber incidents can rapidly create cross-sector, cross-border and security-relevant impacts. Building on the findings of the COcyber Needs Assessment, PESTEL analysis, national case studies from Lithuania, Spain, Hungary and Slovenia, a policy and literature review and a structured validation process with the COcyber Community and consortium partners, the deliverable identifies key governance, legal, operational and capability gaps affecting effective cooperation. The recommendations focus on improving civil–defence

coordination interfaces, trusted information sharing, protected incident reporting, joint exercises, skills development, dual-use innovation, funding alignment, strategic autonomy, policy monitoring and common terminology. Rather than proposing a single model for all Member States, the deliverable supports an adaptable and implementation-oriented approach that respects national competences while strengthening European added value through interoperability, trust, preparedness and continuous policy learning.

Keywords

Civilian–defence cybersecurity coordination, EU cybersecurity policy, cyber resilience, information sharing, protected incident reporting, cyber crisis management, EU–NATO cooperation, dual-use cybersecurity, strategic autonomy, digital sovereignty, cybersecurity capability development, cyber skills, joint cyber exercises, trusted cooperation, cybersecurity governance, policy learning

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* Deliverable types:

R: document, report (excluding periodic and final reports).

DEM: demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs.

DEC: websites, patent filings, press and media actions, videos, etc.

OTHER: software, technical diagrams, etc.

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Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Description
8ra	European initiative for next-generation cloud infrastructure and services linked to IPCEI-CIS
CDPF	Cyber Defence Policy Framework
CERT	Computer Emergency Response Team, a group of information security experts who identify, analyse and mitigate cybersecurity incidents and threats.
CERT-EU	Computer Emergency Response Team for the EU institutions, bodies and agencies
CFSP	Common Foreign and Security Policy
COcyber	Coordination between the Cybersecurity Civilian and Defence Spheres. It is the project to which this booklet belongs—specifically, it is part of Task 4.1 within Work Package 4.
CSDP	Common Security and Defence Policy
CSIRT	Computer Security Incident Response Team
CSIRTs Network	EU network of national Computer Security Incident Response Teams
DIANA	NATO Defence Innovation Accelerator for the North Atlantic
ECCC	The European Cybersecurity Competence Centre, the funding authority of the COcyber project.
EDA	European Defence Agency
EDIH	European Digital Innovation Hub
ECSF	Cybersecurity Skills Framework
EIC	European Innovation Council
ENISA	European Union Agency for Cybersecurity

ESDC	European Security and Defence College
ETEE	Education, Training, Evaluation and Exercise
EU	The European Union (EU) is a political and economic union of 27 European countries, designed to foster economic cooperation, promote peace, and create a single market with free movement of goods, services, and people.
EU-CyCLONe	European Cyber Crisis Liaison Organisation Network
EUCC	EU Common Criteria-based cybersecurity certification scheme
EUDIS	EU Defence Innovation Scheme
ICRC	International Committee of the Red Cross
ICT	Information and Communication Technology
IHL	International Humanitarian Law
IPCEI	Important Project of Common European Interest
IPCEI-CIS	Important Project of Common European Interest on Next Generation Cloud Infrastructure and Services
IPCR	Integrated Political Crisis Response
ISACs	Information Sharing and Analysis Centres, non-profit organisations that provide a central resource for gathering information on cyberthreats.
M&E	Monitoring and Evaluation
MICNET	EU Military Computer Emergency Response Teams Operational Network
NCC / NCCC	National Coordination Centre / National Cybersecurity Coordination Centre
NIS 2	Directive (EU) 2022/2555 (updated Network and Information Systems Directive).
PCP	Pre-Commercial Procurement
PESCO	Permanent Structured Cooperation
PESTEL	Political, Economic, Social, Technological, Environmental and Legal analysis
PPI	Public Procurement of Innovative Solutions
PQC	Post-Quantum Cryptography

R&D	Research and Development
SAFE	Security Action for Europe
SME	Small and Medium-size Enterprises
SOC	Security Operations Centre
STIX/TAXII	Standardised threat intelligence formats (mentioned in the context of protocol standardisation)
TTOs	Technology Transfer Offices

Executive Summary

This deliverable presents the COCyber policy recommendations for strengthening civilian–defence cybersecurity coordination in Europe. It responds to a growing policy and operational challenge: cybersecurity threats increasingly affect the infrastructures, services, supply chains, technologies and actors that are shared across civilian, defence, public–sector, private–sector and research communities. Cyber incidents affecting critical infrastructure, cloud services, telecommunications, transport, energy, health systems, public administration or digital supply chains can quickly acquire defence, crisis–management or hybrid–threat relevance. As a result, closer coordination between civilian and defence cybersecurity actors is no longer only a strategic ambition, but a practical requirement for resilience, preparedness and response.

The analysis confirms that civilian and defence cybersecurity are increasingly interdependent. Cyber incidents affecting energy, transport, telecommunications, cloud services, health systems, public administration, space–based services or supply chains can quickly become relevant for defence readiness, crisis management and hybrid–threat response. However, civil–defence cooperation remains difficult because civilian cybersecurity is mainly shaped through EU internal–market, resilience and regulatory instruments, while defence and national security remain primarily Member State competences. This creates a persistent coordination gap between EU–level policy frameworks and national operational realities.

The strongest policy result is that governance, trusted information sharing and protected incident reporting should be treated as a single connected implementation cluster. Governance provides the institutional basis for cooperation; trusted information sharing provides the operational channel; and protected incident reporting creates a practical mechanism for turning cyber incidents into lessons learned, early warning and shared situational awareness. The deliverable therefore recommends clearer national civil–defence coordination interfaces, trusted contact points, controlled sharing channels, agreed escalation procedures, confidentiality safeguards, anonymisation and sanitisation mechanisms, and feedback loops for reporting entities.

The deliverable also finds that civil–defence cybersecurity capability development should be treated as a full lifecycle. This means connecting needs identification, research funding, technology validation, SME support, skills development, exercises, procurement, certification, deployment, monitoring and policy review. This is particularly important for dual–use cybersecurity technologies, where civilian innovation can have defence relevance and defence needs may depend on commercial or civilian–origin technologies. The recommendations therefore call for stronger links between EU funding instruments, procurement guidance, certification schemes, operational demand and innovation uptake.

Another main result concerns skills, exercises and operational preparedness. The analysis shows that strategic ambition often exceeds operational capacity. Civilian and defence actors need more regular joint exercises, cyber ranges, red-team/blue-team formats, scenario-based planning, cyber reserve models and lessons-learned mechanisms. These activities should test not only technical response, but also governance arrangements, escalation routes, secure information exchange, classification handling, public-private cooperation and coordination between civilian and defence authorities.

The deliverable further concludes that strategic autonomy and digital sovereignty must be made operational. They should not remain rhetorical concepts. Practical implementation should focus on dependency mapping, trusted procurement requirements, certification links, supply-chain assurance, secure cloud and infrastructure choices, investment priorities and monitoring indicators. Full autonomy in areas such as cloud, AI, supply chains or secure infrastructure is not realistic in the short term. However, by 2028, the EU and Member States can establish the governance, mapping, funding, procurement and monitoring foundations needed to reduce high-risk dependencies and strengthen trusted European capabilities.

Finally, the deliverable highlights the importance of monitoring, common terminology and continuous policy learning. Civilian and defence actors often use different concepts, procedures and operational vocabularies. A common EU civil-defence cyber glossary and doctrine-like guidance would support more consistent understanding of terms such as cyber crisis, escalation, protected reporting, trusted information sharing, cyber reserve, dual-use cybersecurity technology, operational readiness, hybrid threats and strategic autonomy. Monitoring and peer-learning mechanisms should also feed lessons from incidents, exercises, funding outcomes and stakeholder feedback back into EU and national policy development.

Overall, Deliverable D4.5 concludes that the next phase of European cybersecurity policy should focus on operationalising existing frameworks. The priority is to build trusted interfaces, shared procedures, practical cooperation channels, interoperable capabilities and continuous learning mechanisms that allow civilian and defence actors to coordinate before, during and after major cyber incidents. The final COcyber recommendations therefore provide an implementation-oriented policy package for strengthening European cyber resilience, civil-defence cooperation and long-term preparedness.

1 Introduction

Cybersecurity has become a central pillar of European security, resilience and competitiveness. Across the European Union, digital infrastructures, critical services, public administrations, defence systems, supply chains and private-sector operators are increasingly interconnected. This interdependence creates major opportunities for

innovation and operational efficiency, but it also exposes Europe to complex cyber threats that cut across traditional institutional, sectoral and national boundaries. Cyber incidents affecting energy, transport, health, telecommunications, cloud services, public administration or digital supply chains can rapidly generate consequences for both civilian resilience and defence preparedness. As a result, the coordination between civilian and defence cybersecurity actors is no longer a secondary policy concern, but a practical requirement for effective crisis prevention, preparedness, response and recovery.

The EU has developed a broad and increasingly sophisticated cybersecurity policy framework. Instruments such as the NIS2 Directive, the Critical Entities Resilience Directive, the Cybersecurity Act, the Cyber Resilience Act and the Cyber Solidarity Act have strengthened the Union's approach to cyber resilience, risk management, incident reporting, certification, product security and operational support. In parallel, the Strategic Compass, the EU Policy on Cyber Defence, PESCO cyber initiatives and wider EU–NATO cooperation have reinforced the defence and security dimension of cyber policy. However, the interaction between these civilian and defence frameworks remains complex. Civilian cybersecurity is largely shaped by the EU internal-market, resilience and regulatory instruments, while defence and national security remain primarily Member State responsibilities. This creates a persistent coordination challenge: Europe needs stronger interoperability, information sharing and preparedness across civilian and defence communities, while still respecting national competencies, confidentiality requirements and the distinct mandates of different actors.

This deliverable responds to that challenge by developing policy recommendations to strengthen civilian–defence cybersecurity coordination in Europe. It forms part of the COcyber project's wider objective to enhance exchange, coordination and collaboration between civilian and defence cybersecurity spheres. The recommendations are intended to support EU and Member State reflection on how to move from broad strategic ambition towards more practical, trusted and implementation-oriented cooperation. They do not propose a single institutional model for all Member States. Instead, they aim to identify common principles, operational interfaces and policy actions that can be adapted to different national contexts, levels of maturity and institutional arrangements.

The recommendations are grounded in a multi-layered evidence base. The deliverable draws on a literature and policy review, previous COcyber work including the Needs Assessment and PESTEL analysis, and the findings of national case studies carried out in Lithuania, Spain, Hungary and Slovenia. These sources provide insight into existing policy frameworks, implementation barriers, national practices, stakeholder needs and emerging gaps. The analysis also reflects the broader European and international policy environment, including the growing importance of resilience, technological sovereignty, dual-use capability development, trusted information sharing, supply-chain security and whole-of-society preparedness.

The development of the recommendations followed a participatory approach. Preliminary findings and draft recommendations were tested through COcyber policy-oriented workshops, stakeholder exchanges and internal consortium validation. This process helped assess whether the recommendations were realistic, policy-relevant and sufficiently sensitive to differences between Member States, sectors and institutional cultures. It also helped refine the recommendations by identifying implementation barriers, possible lead actors, short-, medium- and long-term actions, and areas where EU-level added value is strongest.

The purpose of this deliverable is therefore twofold. First, it consolidates the main policy lessons emerging from COcyber's research, consultation and validation activities. Second, it translates those lessons into practical recommendations that can support more coherent and resilient cybersecurity cooperation across Europe. By doing so, the deliverable contributes to the broader European policy shift from fragmented, sector-based cybersecurity towards a more integrated model of preparedness, where civilian and defence actors are better able to coordinate before, during and after major cyber incidents.

2 Methodological approach

The formulation of policy recommendations within the COcyber project is underpinned by a comprehensive, multi-phased methodological framework that combines empirical data collection with systematic stakeholder engagement. This approach ensures analytical rigour, policy relevance, and alignment with both national contexts and overarching European cybersecurity objectives. The methodology is structured into two interdependent phases:

Phase 1. Data collection, review, and analytical synthesis. This phase integrates multiple data sources to construct a robust evidence base for the development of preliminary policy recommendations. It includes both desk research and the comparative analysis of empirical findings from national-level case studies.

Literature and policy review. This consists of a structured review of academic and grey literature conducted to map the current state of knowledge on cybersecurity policy, technology transfer, and information sharing. The review is based on the work conducted in **the D2.2 NEEDS Assessment**¹ and **D4.4 PESTEL Analysis**.² Key sources include: Peer-reviewed articles from journals in cybersecurity, technology governance, and public policy; strategic documents from the European Commission (e.g., the NIS 2 Directive, the EU Cybersecurity Strategy, the Digital Europe Programme); publications by EU agencies such

¹ <https://zenodo.org/records/16760899>

² <https://zenodo.org/records/14800487>

as ENISA and the European Defence Agency (EDA), as well as reports from think tanks and relevant EU-funded projects. This review supports the identification of trends, gaps, and best practices in both policy and implementation domains.

Integration of case study findings. Building on Deliverable 4.2 *National Case Studies Booklet on Cybersecurity Technology and Information Transfer*, the findings from the four national case studies (Lithuania, Spain, Hungary, and Slovenia) are systematically analysed.³ Each case provides preliminary policy recommendations based on national practices and stakeholder insights. These are reviewed and synthesised through a comparative lens to identify convergences and divergences across Member States; highlight policy innovations and bottlenecks; and establish a foundation for generalisable, EU-relevant recommendations.

Thematic categorisation. Emergent themes from the literature review and case studies are thematically categorised into key policy domains (e.g., governance, legal frameworks, innovation, capacity building, dual-use technologies). This analytical process facilitates the structuring of recommendations around coherent thematic areas, ensuring alignment with both empirical insights and policy relevance.

Phase 2. Participatory validation and refinement. To enhance the legitimacy, feasibility, and applicability of the proposed recommendations, a rigorous multi-stakeholder validation process is conducted through 4 policy-oriented workshops, engaging the COcyber ambassadors, and internal validation by the COcyber Consortium Partners. This phase reflects COcyber's commitment to participatory policy-making and stakeholder co-creation.

Engagement with the COcyber Community and EU collaborating projects (Task 6.1). Draft recommendations are then validated through concertation activities under WP4 and Task 6.1, which include workshops with COcyber Community members and other EU-funded cybersecurity projects. Specifically, **four policy-related workshops** were carried out, three online and one in person. This process aims to validate the initial set of policy recommendations by the COcyber Community and foster cross-project learning and coherence, benchmark COcyber's proposals against other initiatives, as well as enhance policy harmonisation and alignment.

Internal validation by COcyber consortium partners. A final round of validation is conducted within the COcyber consortium. Partners will review the updated recommendations to ensure consistency with project objectives and work package outcomes, as well as technical and contextual soundness. On the positive side, consortium partners had first-hand access to genuine expert community feedback as they conducted the interviews. On the flip side, there is some potential concern that consortium partners

³ <https://zenodo.org/records/17972745>

are reviewing their own, albeit consolidated, recommendations made in the country case studies authored by themselves.

3 Data gathering processes

3.1 Literature and policy review

The coordination of civilian and defence cybersecurity in the European Union is shaped by a persistent jurisdictional fault line. Civilian cybersecurity is largely pursued through internal-market, resilience, and regulatory instruments, while defence and national security remain primarily matters of Member State responsibility and are governed mainly through intergovernmental mechanisms under the Common Foreign and Security Policy (CFSP) and the Common Security and Defence Policy (CSDP). This distinction is visible across the EU Law. Instruments such as NIS2, the Critical Entities Resilience (CER) Directive, the Cybersecurity Act, the Cyber Resilience Act, and the Cyber Solidarity Act build coordination through harmonisation and resilience, whereas cyber defence initiatives rely more heavily on Council endorsed policy frameworks, capability cooperation, and voluntary coordination among Member States.⁴

A second competence boundary appears in EU external action. The EU's horizontal cyber sanctions regime is built on a dual legal basis: restrictive measures are politically established through CFSP rules and then implemented through a regulation under Article 215 TFEU. The cyber sanctions framework itself reflects this two-step model, combining Council Decision (CFSP) 2019/797 with Council Regulation (EU) 2019/796. This architecture matters because it allows the EU to impose Union-wide consequences such as asset freezes and travel bans, while still keeping the measures subject to EU legal discipline and judicial review. It is also a reminder that coordinated cyber response is not only technical or operational; it can also involve diplomacy, attribution, signalling, and economic coercive tools.⁵

A third legal boundary concerns procurement and capability development. EU-level procurement rules do apply in defence and security, but the logic of essential security interests under Article 346 TFEU remains a persistent avenue for Member State discretion. EU law treats this exemption as exceptional and subject to justification rather than as a blanket carve-out. That is reflected both in the structure of the defence procurement regime and in case law such as *Commission v Poland*, where the Court scrutinised reliance

⁴ Directive (EU) 2022/2555 on measures for a high common level of cybersecurity across the Union (NIS2); Directive (EU) 2022/2557 on the resilience of critical entities; Regulation (EU) 2019/881 (Cybersecurity Act); Regulation (EU) 2024/2847 (Cyber Resilience Act); Regulation (EU) 2025/38 (Cyber Solidarity Act), EUR-Lex.

⁵ Council Decision (CFSP) 2019/797 of 17 May 2019 concerning restrictive measures against cyber-attacks threatening the Union or its Member States; Council Regulation (EU) 2019/796 of 17 May 2019 concerning restrictive measures against cyber-attacks threatening the Union or its Member States, EUR-Lex.

on essential security interests in procurement-related contexts.⁶ This matters for cyber because sensitive acquisitions such as secure communications, threat-intelligence platforms, cyber ranges, and dual-use security tools often sit precisely in the grey zone between internal-market discipline and national-security discretion.⁷

Another emerging concern are new technologies such as AI and Post-Quantum Cryptography (PQC).⁸ PQC refers to cryptographic methods designed to remain secure against the future capabilities of quantum computers. This is increasingly important because quantum computing could undermine many of the public-key cryptographic systems currently used to protect confidentiality, authenticity, identity management, secure communications and critical digital services. The European Commission has encouraged Member States to prepare a coordinated transition to PQC. For COCyber, PQC is relevant because civilian and defence actors depend on many of the same cryptographic foundations, including secure communications, cloud services, classified or sensitive information exchange, digital identity systems, critical infrastructure protection and long-term data confidentiality. A coordinated PQC transition should therefore be treated not only as a technical upgrade, but as a strategic preparedness issue requiring asset inventories, risk prioritisation, procurement requirements, certification links, skills development and civil-defence coordination.

Sovereignty should also be treated as a central policy frame rather than a side issue. The **Cloud and AI Development Act** has emerged as a major forthcoming initiative in this space.⁹ Commission planning documents assign this file to Executive Vice-President Henna Virkkunen under the broader Tech Sovereignty, Security and Democracy agenda. The European Parliament's briefing on the Cloud and AI Development Act presents the initiative as a response to insufficient EU data-centre capacity, dependence on non-EU providers, and the need for secure EU-based services for highly critical use cases. In parallel, the Commission's *Cloud Sovereignty Framework* provides a structured way to think about sovereignty in operational terms by defining sovereignty objectives relevant to cloud services, rather than reducing the debate to simplistic ownership tests alone. The most useful distinction is not simply European owned versus non-European owned, but whether a platform or service can meet relevant assurance, auditability, continuity, legal-control, and security objectives for critical or defence relevant use cases. That is why the Commission's cloud sovereignty work is important: it helps move the debate from symbolic autonomy toward concrete governance and technical criteria. For cybersecurity coordination between civilian and defence spheres, this matters because shared cloud,

⁶ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=celex:62019CJ0791>

⁷ Article 346 TFEU; Directive 2009/81/EC on defence and security procurement; Court of Justice of the European Union, *European Commission v Republic of Poland*, Case C-601/21, 7 September 2023, EUR-Lex.

⁸ <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/library/coordinated-implementation-roadmap-transition-post-quantum-cryptography>

⁹ <https://www.eu-cloud-ai-act.com/>

data, identity, and AI infrastructures increasingly underpin both operational resilience and crisis response. Initiatives, such as 8ra, will play an important role in Europe's sovereignty.

The **8ra Initiative** is a European strategic initiative linked to the **IPCEI on Next Generation Cloud Infrastructure and Services (IPCEI-CIS)**.¹⁰ It brings together **12 EU Member States** and around **120 industrial and research partners** to strengthen Europe's **digital sovereignty** through a decentralised, interoperable and secure **cloud-edge infrastructure**. Its goal is to create a **Multi-Provider Cloud-Edge Continuum**, allowing IT services, data and workloads to move seamlessly across providers and borders. The initiative promotes **open-source collaboration**, interoperability, security and vendor neutrality, helping European companies, especially SMEs, avoid dependence on dominant non-European cloud providers. 8ra responds to key challenges in Europe's cloud market, including fragmentation, limited interoperability, vendor lock-in, sovereignty concerns and the need to support future technologies such as **AI, industrial IoT, cybersecurity and the metaverse**. It aims to build a resilient and sustainable cloud-edge ecosystem that supports innovation, competitiveness and economic resilience.

3.2 Strategic drivers of civil-defence cyber coordination

Against this legal backdrop, EU and NATO cybersecurity documents increasingly present civil-defence cyber coordination as a **practical necessity**, not simply a long-term policy ambition. Their importance is that they connect three agendas that were often treated separately: **civilian cybersecurity, defence preparedness, and technological sovereignty**.

The EU Cybersecurity Strategy for the Digital Decade provides the broad foundation. It argues that Europe's technological sovereignty depends on the resilience of connected products, services and infrastructures, and that the four cyber communities (internal market, law enforcement, diplomacy and defence) must work more closely towards shared threat awareness and collective response.¹¹ The Strategic Compass then brings this logic into the EU security and defence agenda by setting a common vision for EU security and defence policy by 2030, including stronger resilience, investment, partnerships and protection of contested domains.¹² The EU Policy on Cyber Defence makes the link more concrete by focusing on stronger cyber defence capabilities, cooperation between civilian

¹⁰ [Europe's Next Generation Cloud Infrastructure and Services – 8ra](#)

¹¹ <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/cybersecurity-strategy>

¹² <https://www.consilium.europa.eu/en/policies/strategic-compass/>

and military cyber communities, crisis management, investment and reduced strategic dependencies in critical cyber technologies.¹³

The **EU Military Computer Emergency Response Teams Operational Network (MICNET)** is a cyber-defence initiative intended to strengthen cooperation between military CERTs across the EU.¹⁴ It is relevant to the COcyber deliverable because it provides a concrete defence-side counterpart to civilian cyber cooperation structures such as the CSIRTs Network and EU-CyCLONe. MICNET can help improve military cyber situational awareness, support cooperation between national military cyber-response actors, and create a more structured interface for civil-defence coordination when incidents affect both civilian infrastructure and defence readiness. Its importance lies in the fact that major cyber incidents increasingly cut across institutional boundaries: an attack on telecommunications, cloud services, energy systems or transport infrastructure may require civilian authorities, CSIRTs, defence cyber actors and crisis-management bodies to exchange information and coordinate without confusing their respective mandates. MICNET therefore strengthens the operational basis for civil-military cyber cooperation while preserving the specific role of military cyber structures.

NATO documents move in a similar direction. The 2022 Strategic Concept places cyber within NATO's wider deterrence and defence posture, while NATO's resilience and civil-preparedness work links critical infrastructure, digital networks, continuity of government, essential services and civil support to military operations.¹⁵ This is important because it shows that disruptions to civilian systems, such as telecommunications, cloud services, energy, transport, health systems, digital supply chains or space-based services, can quickly become defence-relevant.

Recent threat assessments strengthen this argument. ENISA's Threat Landscape 2025 analyses 4,875 incidents from 1 July 2024 to 30 June 2025, showing a more complex and professionalised threat environment.¹⁶ ENISA's foresight work also identifies supply-chain compromise, skills shortages, legacy systems, unpatched systems, cross-border ICT providers and hybrid threats among the key long-term risks for 2030.¹⁷ These findings support the case for civil-defence coordination because civilian and defence actors increasingly depend on the same infrastructures, suppliers, software ecosystems and limited cyber workforce.

¹³ <https://eda.europa.eu/news-and-events/press-office/latest-press-releases/2022/11/10/cyber-defence-eu-boosts-action-against-cyber-threats>

¹⁴ https://defence-industry-space.ec.europa.eu/security-and-defence-eu-boosts-action-against-cyber-threats-and-allow-armed-forces-move-faster-and-2022-11-09_en

¹⁵ <https://www.nato.int/en/about-us/official-texts-and-resources/strategic-concepts/nato-2022-strategic-concept>

¹⁶ <https://www.enisa.europa.eu/publications/enisa-threat-landscape-2025>

¹⁷ <https://www.enisa.europa.eu/news/skills-shortage-and-unpatched-systems-soar-to-high-ranking-2030-cyber-threats>

However, the literature is more cautious than the policy documents. It generally agrees that cyber creates strong civil–military interdependence, but warns that cooperation is difficult in practice. Recent research argues that cyber reshapes civil–military relations by blurring authority, increasing reliance on private actors, creating new oversight problems, and expanding the military footprint in domains traditionally linked to civilian governance.¹⁸ Other work warns that the EU’s growing number of cybersecurity policies may increase complexity, institutional overlap and implementation incoherence if roles, mandates and procedures are not clearly aligned.¹⁹ In short, these documents are important because they create the strategic basis for coordination, but they do not fully solve the practical problems of trust, classification, information–sharing, democratic oversight, private–sector dependence and EU–Member State competence boundaries.

Document	Why it matters	Main Contribution	Critical Perspective
EU Cybersecurity Strategy for the Digital Decade ²⁰	Connects cybersecurity with civilian, technological sovereignty and external action.	Creates the strategic logic for bringing law enforcement, diplomatic and defence communities closer together.	Broad and ambitious, but operational coordination still depends on trust, Member State implementation and clear procedures.
Strategic Compass ²¹	Places cyber within the EU’s wider security and defence agenda up to 2030.	Makes cyber, hybrid threats, resilience and contested domains part of EU defence planning.	Strong on strategic ambition, but less clear on how civilian and defence mandates should interact in practice.
EU Policy on Cyber Defence ²²	Translates the Strategic Compass into a more cyber-specific defence agenda.	Focuses on cyber defence capabilities, civil–military coordination, investment, crisis	Still faces major barriers: classification, fragmented funding, different institutional cultures, and limited

¹⁸ *Journal of Cybersecurity*, Volume 12, Issue 1, 2026, tyag012, <https://doi.org/10.1093/cybsec/tyag012>

¹⁹ [arXiv:2405.12043](https://arxiv.org/abs/2405.12043) [cs.CR] <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2405.12043>

²⁰ <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/library/eus-cybersecurity-strategy-digital-decade-0>

²¹ https://www.eeas.europa.eu/eeas/strategic-compass-security-and-defence-1_en

²² https://www.eeas.europa.eu/sites/default/files/documents/Comm_cyber%20defence.pdf

		management and reducing dependencies.	common operational routines.
NATO Strategic Concept 2022 ²³	Confirms cyber as part of NATO's deterrence and defence posture.	Links cyber threats, resilience and collective defence.	NATO's defence framing is operationally useful, but literature warns that it may also contribute to the militarisation of cybersecurity.
NATO resilience and civil preparedness guidance ²⁴	Shows that civilian infrastructure is part of defence readiness.	Connects continuity of government, essential services, civil communications and support to military operations.	Effective resilience depends on national implementation and private-sector infrastructure that NATO does not directly control.
ENISA Threat Landscape 2025 / Foresight 2030 ²⁵	Provides the threat /evidence behind the policy shift.	Shows that supply chains, cross-border ICT providers, skills shortages and hybrid threats affect both civilian and defence preparedness	Threat assessments identify risks clearly, but do not decide who should share what information, under which safeguards, and through which channels.

Table 1 EU Policies

²³ <https://www.nato.int/content/dam/nato/webready/documents/publications-and-reports/strategic-concepts/2022/290622-strategic-concept.pdf>

²⁴ https://www.nato.int/content/dam/nato/legacy-wcm/media_pdf/2020/4/pdf/200414-guidelines-civmilcoop-cbrn.pdf

²⁵ <https://www.enisa.europa.eu/publications/enisa-foresight-cybersecurity-threats-for-2030>

3.3 EU legal and policy architecture shaping coordination

The EU's main coordination engine for the civilian side, and therefore a major enabler for civil–defence cooperation, is the strengthening of national governance under the **NIS2 Directive (2022)**.²⁶

Role: Main EU coordination framework for civilian cybersecurity.

Key contribution:

- Strengthens national cybersecurity governance.
- Requires Member States to establish or reinforce national cybersecurity strategies.
- Requires designation of competent cybersecurity authorities.
- Builds national incident response capacity.
- Connects Member States through EU cooperation structures.

Relevance for civil–defence coordination:

- Defence is not the primary target of NIS2, but the directive shapes how defence actors interact with civilian authorities and critical–sector operators during major cyber incidents.
- It creates the civilian coordination structures that defence actors may need to interface with in crises.

NIS2 is implemented mainly through national governance reform and sectoral compliance. Member States must translate the Directive into national law, designate or reinforce competent authorities, identify essential and important entities, establish national cybersecurity strategies, and ensure that covered organisations apply risk–management and incident–reporting obligations. In practice, this means ministries, regulators and national cybersecurity agencies have to create supervisory procedures, reporting channels, enforcement mechanisms and sector–specific guidance for operators in areas such as energy, transport, health, digital infrastructure, public administration, space and ICT services. The Commission describes NIS2 as a unified framework covering 18 critical sectors and requiring Member States to adopt national cybersecurity strategies and cooperate at EU level for cross–border reaction and enforcement.

²⁶ [Directive - 2022/2555 - EN - EUR-Lex](#)

As part of its new EU cybersecurity package, the Commission proposed a revision of the Cybersecurity Act and targeted changes to the NIS2 Directive.²⁷ The aim is to strengthen EU cyber resilience, reduce fragmented rules, and address growing ICT supply-chain risks. The NIS2 amendments are designed to make compliance clearer and easier for covered entities, while the revised Cybersecurity Act would significantly expand the role of cybersecurity certification, making it a stronger tool for compliance and risk management. The package would also give ENISA a more operational role and introduce stronger EU-level mechanisms to assess, mitigate, and, where necessary, restrict high-risk ICT supply-chain dependencies. The proposals will now be negotiated by the European Parliament and Council, with political agreement targeted for early 2027. Once adopted Member States would have one year to transpose the NIS2 changes into national law.

Critical Entities Resilience Directive – CER Directive (2022)²⁸

Role: Strengthens the resilience of essential services and critical infrastructure.

Key contribution:

- Focuses on continuity of essential services.
- Covers sectors such as energy, transport, health, digital infrastructure, and public administration.
- Encourages preparedness and resilience planning.

Relevance for civil–defence coordination:

- Military readiness depends heavily on civilian infrastructure.
- CER supports a whole-of-society preparedness model.
- It links civilian resilience directly to defence resilience, especially in crises involving host-nation support, logistics, communications, or critical infrastructure disruption.

The CER Directive is implemented through national resilience strategies, risk assessments and the identification of critical entities. Its practical focus is not primarily technical cybersecurity, but continuity of essential services. Member States must adopt national strategies for the resilience of critical entities and carry out risk assessments. The Commission notes that the Directive entered into application on 18 October 2024 and that Member States must identify critical entities in the relevant sectors. In practice, this requires national authorities to map critical services, assess interdependencies, define resilience measures, and engage directly with operators. The implementation challenge is that resilience planning often remains sectoral, while real crises cut across sectors. A

²⁷ <https://www.mcdermottlaw.com/insights/new-eu-cybersecurity-package-what-the-proposed-reforms-mean-for-companies-in-the-eu/>

²⁸ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/dir/2022/2557/oj>

cyberattack affecting ports, rail, energy, telecoms and cloud services would require coordination across several authorities, operators and possibly defence actors.

This same preparedness logic is echoed in the Niinisto report, which calls for stronger operational coordination between civilian and military cyber actors and better fit between emerging EU cyber capabilities and broader preparedness arrangements.²⁹

Cybersecurity Act (2019)

Role: Establishes the EU cybersecurity certification framework and strengthens ENISA's mandate.

Key contribution:

- Creates EU-wide cybersecurity certification schemes.
- Reduces fragmentation in the internal market.
- Strengthens trust and interoperability across digital supply chains.
- Gives ENISA a central role in certification and cooperation.

Relevance for civil–defence coordination:

- Certification can increase trust in technologies used across civilian and defence-adjacent systems.
- ENISA acts as an institutional bridge between Member States, CSIRTs, and EU-level cyber coordination structures.

The Cybersecurity Act and its proposed revision are implemented through certification, ENISA coordination and supply-chain assurance. The original Cybersecurity Act created the EU cybersecurity certification framework and strengthened ENISA's mandate. In practice, implementation takes the form of certification schemes, conformity processes, ENISA guidance, and national cybersecurity certification authorities.

Furthermore, In January 2026, the European Commission proposed a revised Cybersecurity Act to strengthen the EU's cybersecurity resilience, capabilities, and supply-chain security. The proposal would expand ENISA's role by allowing it to issue early cyber threat alerts, support companies affected by ransomware in cooperation with Europol and CSIRTs, provide vulnerability management services, and operate the new single-entry point for incident reporting under the Digital Omnibus. It also introduces a

²⁹ Sauli Niinisto, *Safer Together: Strengthening Europe's Civilian and Military Preparedness and Readiness*, European Commission report, 2024.

trusted ICT supply chain security framework to reduce risks linked to third-country suppliers, using a harmonised, proportionate, and risk-based approach.³⁰

The Cyber Resilience Act (CRA)³¹

Role: Sets horizontal cybersecurity requirements for products with digital elements.

Key contribution:

- Raises baseline cybersecurity requirements for digital products across the EU market.
- Applies to commercial technologies widely used in both civilian and defence-adjacent systems.
- Improves product security before products enter the market.

Relevance for civil–defence coordination:

- Many defence-relevant systems rely on commercial digital components.
- Stronger product security reduces shared vulnerabilities across civilian and defence supply chains.
- Supports interoperability and trust across the wider cybersecurity ecosystem.

The Cyber Resilience Act is implemented through product-security obligations across the digital supply chain. Unlike NIS2, which focuses on organisations and sectors, the CRA focuses on products with digital elements. In practice, manufacturers must design, develop and maintain hardware and software products with cybersecurity requirements throughout their lifecycle, including vulnerability handling, security updates and incident reporting. The CRA entered into force on 10 December 2024 and introduced common standards for hardware and software products, including secure-by-design/default obligations and lifecycle requirements. From 11 September 2026, manufacturers are required to report actively exploited vulnerabilities and severe incidents affecting product security.

EU-level response capacity has also been expanded by the **Cyber Solidarity Act**.³²

Role: Strengthens EU-level detection, preparedness, and response to major cybersecurity threats.

³⁰ European Commission, proposal package of 20 January 2026 amending the NIS2 Directive and revising the Cybersecurity Act, including measures to simplify compliance and strengthen EU cybersecurity certification and ENISA's role, European Commission official materials.

³¹ Regulation (EU) 2019/881 (Cybersecurity Act), EUR-Lex; Regulation (EU) 2024/2847 (Cyber Resilience Act), EUR-Lex; ENISA operational-cooperation and certification materials, ENISA official sources.

³² [Regulation - EU - 2025/38 - EN - EUR-Lex](#)

Key contribution:

- Supports a European cyber alert system.
- Creates an emergency mechanism for major cyber incidents.
- Funds EU-level cyber capabilities through the Digital Europe Programme.
- Encourages mutual support between Member States.

Relevance for civil–defence coordination:

- Large-scale cyber crises often affect civilian infrastructure that defence actors also depend on.
- The Cyber Solidarity Act adds an EU-level capacity layer for detection, response, and support.
- It strengthens preparedness for cross-border incidents that may have both civilian and security implications.

The Cyber Solidarity Act is implemented through EU-level detection, preparedness and emergency-response capacity. In practice, it adds a more operational EU layer to cybersecurity cooperation by creating mechanisms for stronger detection, preparedness and response to major incidents. The regulation aims to strengthen the EU's capacity to detect, prepare for and respond to cyber threats and incidents, including through a European Cybersecurity Alert System, a Cybersecurity Emergency Mechanism and an incident review mechanism. The most concrete implementation step is the EU Cybersecurity Reserve: in August 2025, the Commission entrusted ENISA with operating the Reserve, with €36 million over three years for incident-response services, public procurement of reserve providers and assessment of requests for support.³³ This turns solidarity from a political principle into an operational support mechanism. Its effectiveness will depend on whether Member States request support early enough, whether trusted providers can be mobilised quickly, and whether reserve services are integrated into national crisis plans.

The defence-side architecture rests on **Council-endorsed policy frameworks** and capability cooperation, rather than internal-market harmonisation.

2014 EU Cyber Defence Policy Framework – CDPF

Role: Foundational EU policy framework for cyber defence.

Key contribution:

- Supports cyber defence capabilities for the Common Security and Defence Policy.

³³ <https://www.enisa.europa.eu/news/enisa-to-operate-the-eu-cybersecurity-reserve-with-eur-36-million>

- Enhances protection of CSDP communication networks.
- Promotes civil–military cooperation.
- Encourages synergies with wider EU cybersecurity policies.
- Supports cooperation with international partners.

Relevance for civil–defence coordination:

- Establishes civil–military cooperation as a core element of EU cyber defence policy.
- Provides the early policy basis for linking defence cyber capabilities with broader EU cybersecurity structures.

The Strategic Compass (2022)

Role: Broader EU security and defence framework guiding action up to 2030.

Key contribution:

- Places cyber within the EU’s wider security and defence agenda.
- Supports capability development and crisis response.
- Provides strategic direction for cyber–related CSDP ambitions.

Relevance for civil–defence coordination:

- Frames cyber as part of the EU’s broader security posture.
- Links cybersecurity, defence readiness, crisis response, and resilience.
- Helps connect cyber defence priorities with EU strategic autonomy and preparedness objectives.

2022 Joint Communication on the EU Policy on Cyber Defence

Role: Updates and deepens the EU’s cyber defence policy direction.

Key contribution:

- Aims to strengthen cyber defence capabilities.
- Promotes stronger coordination between EU cyber communities.
- Seeks to reduce strategic dependencies in critical cyber technologies.
- Recognises cyber as a military operational domain.
- Calls for coordinated implementation through military staff structures.

Relevance for civil–defence coordination:

- Directly addresses the need to connect civilian and military cyber communities.
- Moves cyber defence policy from general cooperation towards more structured coordination.
- Highlights the importance of reducing dependency on critical external technologies.

Council Conclusions of May 2023

Role: Political endorsement of the updated EU cyber defence policy direction.

Key contribution:

- Endorses the 2022 EU Policy on Cyber Defence.
- Highlights the need for enhanced civil–military coordination.
- Underlines that there is no hierarchy between civilian and military cyber communities.

Relevance for civil–defence coordination:

- Provides political backing for closer civilian–military cooperation.
- Clarifies that cooperation should respect the distinct roles and mandates of civilian and military actors.
- Reinforces the need for coordination without institutional subordination.

Cyber defence policy is implemented mainly through capability cooperation, military structures and voluntary Member State coordination. The Strategic Compass, EU Policy on Cyber Defence and 2023 Council Conclusions provide strategic direction, but their implementation depends on Member States, the EU Military Staff, EDA, PESCO projects, EDF-funded capability development and national cyber-defence commands. The EU Policy on Cyber Defence moves from general cooperation towards more structured civil–military coordination and reduced dependencies in critical cyber technologies. In practice, however, this is slower and more politically sensitive than civilian cybersecurity implementation because cyber defence involves classified information, national capabilities, intelligence, rules of engagement and military operational planning. Implementation therefore tends to occur through exercises, liaison arrangements, capability projects, cyber ranges, operational concepts and trusted communities rather than binding EU-wide harmonisation.

Capability and operational cooperation is increasingly channelled through **PESCO cyber initiatives**.

PESCO Cyber Rapid Response Teams

Role: Operational cooperation project under Permanent Structured Cooperation.

Key contribution:

- Supports participating Member States in responding to cyber incidents.
- Improves cyber resilience.
- Encourages structured cooperation between Member States.
- Includes cooperation with EU and NATO-related entities.

Relevance for civil–defence coordination:

- Provides a practical mechanism for cyber crisis support.
 - Helps translate policy coordination into deployable capabilities.
 - Strengthens links between national cyber defence actors, EU structures, and partner organisations.
-
- Crisis management and operational coordination mechanisms

The EU’s cyber crisis–management architecture has moved from a general coordination model towards a more operational, lifecycle–based framework. The **2017 Commission Recommendation on a coordinated response to large–scale cybersecurity incidents and crises** established the first EU “Blueprint”, setting out how Member States, EU institutions and existing crisis–management mechanisms should cooperate during major cyber incidents.

The **2025 Council Recommendation on an EU Blueprint for cyber crisis management**, often referred to as the **Cyber Blueprint**, updates this approach. It reflects the newer EU cybersecurity landscape, including **NIS2**, the **Cyber Solidarity Act**, and the growing need to connect technical, operational, political and, where relevant, military actors.³⁴

What the Cyber Blueprint adds

The updated Blueprint is important because it makes EU cyber crisis management more structured, practical and connected to existing legal and operational frameworks.

Its main contribution is to clarify:

- **Who does what** during a large–scale cyber incident.
- **How information should flow** between technical, operational and political levels.

³⁴ [EUR-Lex - 32025H03445 - EN - EUR-Lex](#)

- **When escalation is needed** from technical coordination to political crisis response.
- **How EU-level mechanisms** such as the CSIRTs Network, EU-CyCLONe, ENISA and the IPCR should interact.
- **How civilian and military actors can coordinate**, especially when cyber incidents affect critical infrastructure relevant to defence or security.

The Blueprint therefore moves EU cyber crisis management away from ad hoc coordination and towards a more predictable crisis-management cycle.

EU-CyCLONe as the operational bridge³⁵

A central element of the EU crisis-management framework is **EU-CyCLONe**, established under **Article 16 of the NIS2 Directive**.

EU-CyCLONe connects national cyber crisis-management authorities and acts as a bridge between:

- **Technical responders**, especially the CSIRTs Network.
- **National crisis-management authorities**.
- **EU-level political decision-making structures**, including crisis response mechanisms such as the IPCR.

Its role is not to replace national responsibility, but to support a coordinated EU response when incidents are too large or cross-border to be managed in isolation.

EU-CyCLONe contributes by:

- Building a shared situational picture of major cyber incidents.
- Assessing operational, economic and societal impacts.
- Supporting the coordination of mitigation measures across Member States.
- Helping align national cyber crisis-response plans.
- Facilitating secure information exchange on incidents, threats and trends.
- Providing political decision-makers with operational evidence and impact assessments.

Civil-military coordination: a stronger formal hook

³⁵ <https://www.enisa.europa.eu/topics/eu-incident-response-and-cyber-crisis-management/eu-cyclone>

One of the most relevant developments in the updated Cyber Blueprint is the clearer recognition of **military actors** in cyber crisis management.

This matters because many cyber incidents affecting civilian infrastructure may also have defence or security implications. For example, attacks on energy systems, telecommunications, transport, cloud services or satellite infrastructure can affect both civilian continuity and military readiness.

The updated Blueprint therefore creates a stronger basis for:

- Defence liaison within civilian cyber crisis processes.
- Deconfliction between civilian and military responses.
- Coordination with NATO where relevant.
- Joint situational awareness when incidents affect shared dependencies.
- More structured cooperation before crises occur, rather than improvising during emergencies.

This is a significant step because civil–military cyber coordination has often been recognised as necessary but remained difficult to operationalise in practice.

Operational coordination tools and situational awareness

EU cyber crisis management also depends on shared tools, inventories and contact structures.

ENISA supports the civilian cyber ecosystem through resources such as:

- CSIRT inventories.
- CSIRTs by Country interactive mapping.³⁶
- Recurring updates on national CSIRT structures.
- Support to EU–level preparedness and coordination processes.

These tools are civilian by design, but they are also relevant for defence coordination because they help identify:

- Who the responsible civilian cyber authorities are.
- Where technical response capacity exists.
- How national cyber response structures are organised.
- Which contact points may be needed during cross–sector incidents.

³⁶ [CSIRTs by Country - Interactive Map | ENISA](#)

For civil–defence coordination, this kind of visibility is essential. Defence actors often depend on civilian infrastructure and civilian authorities during systemic cyber incidents.

Capability development and dual–use cooperation

The EU crisis–management framework is complemented by capability–building initiatives in both civilian and defence domains.

Relevant EU defence and dual–use initiatives include:

- **Cyber Rapid Response Teams and Mutual Assistance in Cyber Security**, developed under Permanent Structured Cooperation, which supports incident response and resilience.
- **Cyber Ranges Federations**, which aims to connect national cyber ranges and strengthen joint training capacity.
- EU and NATO innovation pathways that support dual–use technologies relevant to cyber defence, resilience and crisis response.

NATO’s **Defence Innovation Accelerator for the North Atlantic** also reflects this wider trend by promoting technologies that can serve both civilian and defence security needs.³⁷

These initiatives matter because cyber crisis management is not only about procedures. It also requires:

- Trained personnel.
- Shared exercises.
- Interoperable tools.
- Trusted operational relationships.
- Technologies that can be used across civilian and defence contexts.

Information sharing as a core requirement

The Blueprint places strong emphasis on information sharing across Member States, EU entities and relevant networks.

Information sharing is needed to support:

- Early warning.

³⁷ [DIANA | Home](#)

- Situational awareness.
- Risk assessment.
- Technical mitigation.
- Political decision-making.
- Cross-border coordination.

The 2025 Cyber Blueprint recognises that incidents affecting EU institutions, bodies or agencies can create risks for Member States, and that incidents in Member States can have wider Union-level consequences.

This creates a strong argument for routine information-sharing practices before crises occur, including:

- Common reporting channels.
- Clear escalation procedures.
- Trusted contact points.
- Shared terminology.
- Feedback loops between technical and political levels.

Secure communications and classified information remain major constraints

Despite the stronger coordination framework, secure information exchange remains a structural challenge.

Civil-military cyber coordination often involves sensitive or classified information, especially when incidents concern:

- Defence infrastructure.
- Intelligence-sensitive threat information.
- Critical infrastructure dependencies.
- NATO-related coordination.
- National security risks.
- Ongoing operational responses.

The Cyber Blueprint therefore rightly refers to:

- Secure communication channels.
- Existing arrangements for classified information.
- The need to respect national and EU-level confidentiality rules.

The **EU–NATO Security of Information Agreement** is particularly relevant here because it provides a legal basis for protecting classified information exchanged between the EU and NATO.

This matters for cyber crisis management because effective coordination may require shared situational awareness across both EU and NATO structures.

3.4 Funding

At the EU level, cybersecurity funding is spread across a small number of complementary instruments rather than a single standalone fund. The main operational hub is the **European Cybersecurity Competence Centre (ECCC)** in Bucharest, which implements relevant cybersecurity parts of both the **Digital Europe Programme** and **Horizon Europe** and works with a Network of National Coordination Centres to channel funding into capability–building, research, and industrial development. In practice, this means the EU has created a hybrid funding model: **Digital Europe** is used more for deployment, capacity, infrastructure, and uptake, while **Horizon Europe** supports research and innovation, with the ECCC helping connect these layers into a more coherent cybersecurity ecosystem.

National Cybersecurity Coordination Centres, often referred to at the EU level as **NCCs**, are an important bridge between European cybersecurity policy and national implementation. The ECCC works with a Network of National Coordination Centres, with one centre in each Member State, to strengthen Europe’s cybersecurity capacities, research excellence and industrial competitiveness. These centres can support civil–defence cybersecurity coordination by connecting EU funding priorities with national needs, helping public authorities, industry, SMEs, research organisations, CSIRTs and other relevant actors access expertise, funding and capability–building opportunities. In the COcyber context, NCCs are particularly relevant because they can act as national entry points for translating EU–level cybersecurity priorities into practical support for innovation uptake, skills development, cyber capability mapping and stakeholder coordination. Their value is not that they replace national cyber authorities or defence structures, but that they can help align research, funding, industrial development and operational needs across the wider cybersecurity ecosystem.³⁸

The **Digital Europe Programme** is especially important for operational cybersecurity capacity. The Commission describes DIGITAL as supporting the rollout of digital technologies for businesses, citizens, and public administrations, and cybersecurity is one of its core funding areas. Through this programme, the EU funds practical capability measures such as cybersecurity infrastructure, tools, platform development, skills, and

³⁸ https://cybersecurity-centre.europa.eu/nccs_en

wider deployment across Member States, rather than only early-stage research. The ECCC's current calls under Digital Europe show that this programme remains a live funding channel for cybersecurity actions, including projects intended to strengthen Europe's cyber resilience and industrial capacity.

By contrast, **Horizon Europe** is the Union's main research and innovation programme and supports cybersecurity primarily through research-oriented calls, including under the Civil Security for Society cluster and ECCC-managed actions. Its role is to fund the development of new knowledge, emerging technologies, and advanced solutions that can later feed into operational deployment or industrial uptake. This makes Horizon Europe particularly relevant for topics such as advanced cyber tools, experimental solutions, and longer-term innovation agendas, including research with cross-border and strategic significance. The ECCC's 2026 Horizon call and the Cluster 3 work programme both confirm that cybersecurity remains an active and explicitly funded strand within Horizon Europe.

For projects with a stronger **defence or dual-use dimension**, the **European Defence Fund (EDF)** is the key mechanism. The Commission states that the EDF supports collaborative defence research and development across Member States and has a total 2021–2027 budget of nearly **€7.3 billion**. While the EDF is not a general civilian cybersecurity instrument, it is highly relevant for cyber capabilities with defence applications, interoperable technologies, and wider defence innovation. In addition, the **EU Defence Innovation Scheme (EUDIS)** sits within the EDF and is designed to stimulate defence innovation, which can also matter for cybersecurity where civilian and defence use cases overlap.

Funding has become an increasingly important enabler of civil-defence cyber coordination, especially in dual-use contexts. **SAFE**, which entered into force on 29 May 2025, provides up to **EUR150 billion** in loans to support Member States' defence investments through common procurement. Although SAFE is not a cybersecurity-only instrument, it is highly relevant to dual-use cyber capabilities because it can help finance the industrial and procurement shifts needed to bring civilian-origin technologies and suppliers into defence-relevant settings. This is particularly important given the growing view that in cybersecurity, dual use is becoming less of a niche label and more of a baseline condition, since many innovations can potentially move across civilian and defence markets. **NATO DIANA** points in the same direction by supporting deep-tech and explicitly dual-use innovation across the Alliance.

Taken together, these mechanisms show that EU cybersecurity funding is increasingly organised around a **pipeline logic**: research is supported through Horizon Europe, operational capacity and deployment through Digital Europe, and defence-oriented capability development through the EDF, with the ECCC acting as a central coordination and implementation actor for the civilian side. This structure is also meant to reduce

fragmentation and create stronger links between cybersecurity research, industrial development, and practical resilience across the Union.

3.5 EU–NATO cooperation and persistent friction points

Institutional EU–NATO cyber cooperation is anchored in practical technical information-sharing mechanisms and reinforced by political declarations. A long-standing operational milestone is the 2016 Technical Arrangement between CERT-EU and NATO Computer Incident Response Capability, described by the European External Action Service as facilitating technical information-sharing to improve prevention, detection and response while respecting decision-making autonomy. NATO documentation also records this arrangement as a concrete cooperation artefact.³⁹

At the political level, the **EU–NATO Joint Declaration** of 10 January 2023 frames the partnership as mutually reinforcing, calls for closer cooperation, and explicitly situates this within the **NATO Strategic Concept and the EU Strategic Compass**. NATO also announced a task force on resilience and critical infrastructure protection in early 2023, underscoring that the cooperation agenda extends beyond cyber networks to the resilience of the infrastructures on which both civilian society and defence systems rely.⁴⁰

Despite this progress, recurring friction points remain stable in the literature: role clarity in crisis (who leads and when support is requested), information-sharing constraints driven by classification and sensitivity, and uneven interoperability and trust across Member State governance models and private-sector operators. Recent academic analysis of EU cyber crisis management argues that even with new laws and governance bodies, how “cyber crisis management” works in practice at the EU level can remain unclear, strengthening the case for more detailed operationalisation and exercises that explicitly bind civilian and defence participation into the same playbooks.⁴¹

A related strand of scholarship on EU cyber diplomacy and external action highlights that coordinated response is not only technical: it can involve attribution, diplomatic signalling, and restrictive measures, which depend on cross-community inputs that often span civilian, intelligence, diplomatic, and defence spheres. This reinforces COcyber’s emphasis

³⁹ [EU and NATO cyber defence cooperation | EEAS](#)

⁴⁰ [Joint Declaration on EU-NATO Cooperation, 10 January 2023 - Consilium](#)

⁴¹ [From cyber security incident management to cyber security crisis management in the European Union - ScienceDirect](#)

on the need for structured collaboration mechanisms, because whole-of-government cyber response processes fail when evidence, authorities, or decision-making are siloed.⁴²

Competences and Skills

A further area requiring more structured policy attention is the mobilisation of the civilian cybersecurity talent pool during periods of conflict, armed confrontation, or severe hybrid escalation. Current EU cybersecurity frameworks have strengthened crisis coordination, cyber defence cooperation, detection, preparedness and incident response, but they do not yet provide a mature framework for how civilian cyber experts, private-sector specialists, ethical hackers, cyber volunteers or patriotic hacker communities should be governed when conflict-related cyber activity intensifies. EU-CyCLONe, for example, is designed as an operational crisis-management bridge between Member State cyber crisis authorities and the Commission, while the Cyber Solidarity Act focuses on cyber hubs, detection capacity, emergency support and incident review. These are important institutional tools, but they do not fully address the legal status, permissible roles, accountability mechanisms or command interfaces for civilian digital contributors in conflict-related contexts.⁴³

The Tallinn Manual 2.0 remains the key reference for interpreting how existing international law applies to cyber operations, including questions of sovereignty, state responsibility, due diligence, the use of force and international humanitarian law.⁴⁴ However, it is an expert manual rather than a binding legal instrument, and it does not remove the practical uncertainty surrounding decentralised civilian cyber participation. More recent IHL scholarship has therefore focused specifically on hacktivists, volunteer IT armies, patriotic hackers and other civilian cyber actors, highlighting the risks of unclear attribution, escalation, unintended harm to civilian infrastructure, and blurred lines between protected civilian activity and participation in hostilities.

Preparedness policy should therefore distinguish clearly between **lawful defensive mobilisation** and **uncontrolled offensive cyber activity**. Civilian cybersecurity expertise can be valuable in areas such as incident response, malware analysis, vulnerability disclosure, threat intelligence, continuity planning, cyber hygiene campaigns, forensic support and resilience assistance to SMEs or critical infrastructure operators. These roles can strengthen national and European resilience without encouraging civilians to engage in offensive operations against foreign systems. By contrast, ad hoc calls for volunteers to conduct disruption, defacement, DDoS attacks, data leaks or retaliatory hacking create major legal and operational risks, particularly when targets, effects and chains of command are unclear.

⁴² [The Externalisation of the EU's Cybersecurity Regime: The Cyber Diplomacy Toolbox](#)

⁴³ https://www.nis-2-directive.com/NIS_2_Directive_Article_16.html

⁴⁴ <https://www.atlanticcouncil.org/news/press-releases/tallinn-manual-2-0-clarifies-how-international-law-applies-to-cyber-operations/>

For EU and Member State preparedness planning, this implies the need for a clearer governance model. Such a model should define who can be mobilised, under what authority, for which tasks, and with what safeguards. It should also establish vetting procedures, liability rules, codes of conduct, reporting channels, deconfliction with national authorities, and clear separation between civilian defensive support and military or intelligence operations. Particular attention should be paid to SMEs, cybersecurity researchers, open-source intelligence communities and private providers, as these actors may possess valuable expertise but often lack guidance on what is legally permissible during conflict.

The central policy challenge is that Europe has a strong need for civilian cyber expertise but lacks a clear framework for using it safely in conflict-related contexts. The risk is not only legal uncertainty for individual volunteers, but also strategic instability: poorly coordinated civilian cyber activity can create attribution problems, provoke retaliation, disrupt civilian infrastructure, or undermine state-controlled crisis management.

For COcyber-style recommendations, the safest framing is to prioritise **defensive mobilisation under public authority**, not offensive volunteer hacking. This means building reserve-style cyber expertise, pre-approved expert pools, incident-response surge mechanisms, and legal guidance for private actors. The key policy message is that civilian talent should be integrated into resilience and recovery functions, while offensive cyber activity should remain subject to strict state control, legal review, and democratic oversight.

3.6 Preliminary policy findings from the national case studies and Needs Assessment

This section consolidates the comparative findings derived from the four national case studies and the previously conducted D2.2 NEEDS Assessment and articulates a series of evidence-based policy recommendations. These recommendations aim to address both the systemic challenges and the strategic opportunities identified across Lithuania, Spain, Hungary, and Slovenia. By leveraging the diversity of national experiences, the proposed actions seek to advance a more integrated, resilient, and innovation-driven European cybersecurity landscape. The recommendations are structured thematically to guide decision-makers at both national and EU levels in strengthening governance, legal coherence, institutional capacity, and technological innovation.

The COcyber recommendations, stemming from D2.2 Needs Assessment, D4.2 National Case studies, and D4.4 PESTEL Analysis, provide a broad evidence base for understanding

how cybersecurity coordination between civilian and defence spheres can be strengthened across Europe. They combine project-level recommendations on short-, medium-, and long-term strategies with comparative findings derived from the national case studies. Taken together, these materials make it possible not only to identify country-specific priorities, but also to establish a wider analytical foundation for EU-relevant recommendations.

This section has three objectives. First, it analyses the recommendations made throughout the COcyber project life cycle, and published in the deliverables D2.2 Needs Assessment, D4.2 National Case studies, and D4.4 PESTEL Analysis, through a comparative lens in order to identify convergences and divergences across the Member States, while also highlighting policy innovations and persistent bottlenecks. Second, it develops a thematic categorisation of the recommendations so that they can be grouped into coherent policy domains, facilitating the creation of structured EU-wide recommendations.⁴⁵ Third, it provides the preliminary policy recommendations that will then be validated and refined in order to develop the final set of COcyber recommendations.

3.7 Comparative analysis of the COcyber recommendations

3.7.1 Convergences across the four Member States

The analysis is based on the results of the COcyber case studies carried out in four countries: Lithuania, Hungary, Spain and Slovenia. These four national analyses provide a useful comparative sample, but they do not cover all 27 Member States and should not be treated as fully representative of the EU as a whole. Their value lies instead in identifying recurring governance problems that appear across different national contexts. In this sense, the case studies should be read as **problem-pattern evidence** rather than as a complete EU-wide assessment.

A first major convergence across the recommendations is the recognition that cybersecurity must be governed as a **cross-sectoral system**, rather than as a narrow technical or organisational function. Lithuania, Spain, Hungary and Slovenia all point, in different ways, to the need for stronger coordination between the state, defence actors, industry, academia, and wider research and innovation communities. This supports the broader COcyber recommendation that Member States should institutionalise cross-sectoral governance bodies with clear mandates, decision-making capacity, and links to EU-level structures. This finding is consistent with the direction of NIS2, which strengthens cooperation through structures such as the NIS Cooperation Group, CSIRTs Network and

⁴⁵ D4.2 Lithuania, Spain, Hungary, and Slovenia case study recommendation sections.

EU-CyCLONe. However, the case studies also suggest that formal structures alone are insufficient: governance bodies need operational routines, trusted contact points, escalation procedures and political authority, otherwise they risk becoming coordination forums without real implementation power.

A second strong convergence concerns **information sharing**. Across the case studies, information sharing is presented not simply as a platform-design issue, but as a trust, governance and legal-certainty issue. Lithuania calls for novel ways to increase trust and for a unified framework acceptable across countries; Spain advocates confidential and legally protected reporting channels, standardised threat-intelligence formats and stronger links between informal and formal information-sharing structures; Hungary stresses transparency, trust-building and regular interaction; and Slovenia recommends formalised procedures, expanded use of MISIP, stronger ISAC visibility, and more systematic cooperation between authorities, operators, service providers and research organisations. This mirrors wider research on cybersecurity information-sharing governance, which shows that legal frameworks and reporting channels often fail when they do not also address trust-building, privacy and proprietary concerns, reciprocity, and the quality and usefulness of shared information.⁴⁶

A third convergence lies in the repeated diagnosis of **skills shortages and workforce-development needs**. Lithuania describes the lack of cybersecurity skills as extreme and requiring urgent national action; Spain links talent shortages to broader resilience weaknesses and low SME maturity; Slovenia frames workforce development as a strategic issue requiring professional profiles, career paths and integration into human-resource planning; and the broader COcyber recommendations place joint training, simulations, exchange programmes and educational reform at the centre of long-term resilience. This strongly aligns with EU-level evidence: the Cyber Skills Academy notes an estimated shortage of 299,000 cybersecurity professionals in the EU in 2024, while 81% of surveyed companies considered difficulties in hiring cybersecurity staff a key cyberattack risk. ENISA's foresight work also places skills shortages among the most serious emerging cyber threats for 2030.⁴⁷

A fourth convergence concerns the need to reduce **legal and procedural fragmentation**, especially around technology transfer, certification, dual-use technologies and cooperation between civilian and defence-related actors. The COcyber recommendations underline that diverging national interpretations can hinder collaboration and technology mobility, while several case studies call for clearer certification processes, legal guidance, harmonised definitions and simplified administrative procedures. This reflects a broader concern in recent EU cyber-policy

⁴⁶ [arXiv:1805.12266](https://arxiv.org/abs/1805.12266) [cs.CY]

⁴⁷ <https://digital-skills-jobs.europa.eu/en/cybersecurity-skills-academy>

research: the expansion of EU cybersecurity legislation has strengthened the overall framework, but it has also increased complexity and created risks of incoherence between sectors, institutions, technologies and Member State practices. The implication for COcyber is that harmonisation should not mean creating another layer of abstract rules; it should focus on practical guidance, model procedures, interoperable templates and common implementation tools.⁴⁸

Overall, the four case studies point to a common analytical conclusion: the main challenge is not simply the absence of cybersecurity policy, but the difficulty of turning policy into **usable coordination capacity**. EU and national frameworks increasingly recognise the need for cooperation, information exchange, skills development and resilience. Yet the case studies show that implementation still depends on softer but decisive factors: trust, clarity of mandates, incentives to share information, administrative capacity, common terminology, and sustained interaction between civilian, defence, public, private and research actors. The policy relevance of the COcyber findings therefore lies in showing where EU-level ambitions meet national-level friction. They also suggest that the most useful recommendations will be those that translate broad principles into concrete governance mechanisms, implementation steps, and operational tools.

3.7.2 Divergences across the four Member States

While the strategic direction is broadly shared, the recommendations diverge significantly in emphasis, maturity, and immediate policy priorities. This divergence should not be read as a weakness of the case studies, but rather as an important finding in itself. It confirms one of the central messages of the COcyber Needs Assessment: civil-defence cybersecurity cooperation cannot be addressed through a single uniform model. The Needs Assessment identified common structural challenges across Europe, including fragmented governance, limited information-sharing, insufficient awareness and skills, weak dual-use technology transfer, lack of policy coordination, limited cross-pollination between communities, innovation gaps, and cultural differences between civilian and defence actors. However, it also stressed that collaboration strategies must be tailored to sector-specific and national contexts.⁴⁹

Spain's recommendations are the most operationally specific and administratively detailed. They reflect an ecosystem that already possesses substantial institutional depth, but remains fragmented across levels of governance and constrained by procedural complexity. Accordingly, Spain prioritises the creation of a National Cybersecurity Centre, stronger coordination across central, regional, and local levels, procurement reform, legal

⁴⁸ [arXiv:2405.12043](https://arxiv.org/abs/2405.12043) [cs.CR]

⁴⁹ D2.2 Needs Assessment <https://zenodo.org/records/16760899>

certainty for public-private R&D partnerships, more agile support for domestic innovation, and a lifecycle approach to dual-use industrial policy. In relation to the Needs Assessment, Spain therefore illustrates a relatively mature system where the main challenge is not the absence of institutions, but the need to improve coordination, simplify interfaces, and make existing structures more usable for innovation, industry and crisis response.⁵⁰

Lithuania's recommendations are more concentrated and security-driven. They emphasise implementation and enforcement of the Cybersecurity Law, the need for broader organisational guidance beyond formally designated entities, the growing importance of hybrid threats in the regional geopolitical context, the clarification of certification and transfer rules, and urgent educational reform to address the shortage of skilled professionals. Lithuania therefore stands out for connecting cybersecurity coordination more directly to the regional threat environment. This is particularly relevant in the broader global policy context, where cyber resilience is increasingly treated not only as a technical or economic issue, but as part of national security, defence preparedness and democratic resilience. Lithuania's case shows how civil-defence cyber coordination becomes more urgent where cyber threats are closely linked to geopolitical pressure, hybrid activity and the protection of critical infrastructure.⁵¹

Hungary's recommendations are more conceptual than institutional. The material emphasises trust-building, differentiated support for information-sharing, the need to improve the transparency and sectoral visibility of national strategy implementation, and the importance of a shared linguistic and conceptual framework for dual-use cybersecurity cooperation. Hungary also uniquely introduces the question of scale, noting that smaller Member States cannot resolve all challenges alone, while also cautioning against an excessively centralised European approach that would underuse the innovation capacity of smaller states. This reflects a wider global cyber policy dilemma: how to reconcile interoperability, harmonisation and shared standards with national autonomy, local innovation ecosystems and different levels of institutional capacity. In this sense, Hungary's recommendations are particularly useful for highlighting that coordination is not only a question of structures, but also of trust, language, incentives and perceived ownership.⁵²

Slovenia's recommendations are the most explicitly systemic and oriented towards strategy renewal. They begin from the premise that the national cybersecurity strategy is outdated and that a revised strategy must be accompanied by measurable objectives, deadlines, responsibilities, an implementation programme, and clear accountability. Slovenia also places strong emphasis on wide participation, strategic bodies for cooperation, intermediary organisations, transparency in outcomes, and regularised

⁵⁰ COcyber, D4.2 Spain case study, sections 7.1-7.5.

⁵¹ COcyber, D4.2 Lithuania case study, sections 7.1-7.5.

⁵² COcyber, D4.2 Hungary case study findings.

defence–industry–research collaboration for dual–use development. This aligns closely with the Needs Assessment’s emphasis on moving beyond ad hoc coordination towards more mature, institutionalised and sustainable forms of cooperation. It also reflects a broader international policy trend: cybersecurity strategies are increasingly expected to be implementation instruments, not only declaratory documents. They must define responsibilities, create feedback loops, connect public and private actors, and support measurable resilience outcomes.⁵³

Taken together, the four cases demonstrate that the COcyber policy recommendations should operate on two levels. At the European level, they should identify common priorities: trusted information–sharing, coordinated crisis management, dual–use innovation pathways, skills development, public–private cooperation, and clearer governance interfaces between civilian and defence actors. These priorities correspond directly to the phased approach of the Needs Assessment, which proposes short–term trust–building and operational exchange, medium–term capacity–building and governance harmonisation, and long–term institutionalisation, innovation and international integration.⁵⁴ At the national level, however, implementation must remain adaptable. Spain requires administrative integration and procurement agility; Lithuania requires security–driven resilience and skills; Hungary requires trust, transparency and conceptual alignment; Slovenia requires strategy renewal and institutional accountability.

This layered interpretation also connects the country findings to the global cyber policy environment. Across the EU, NATO–adjacent debates, international cyber capacity–building discussions, and global resilience initiatives, the same themes increasingly recur: critical infrastructure protection, whole–of–society preparedness, cyber crisis coordination, public–private partnership, technology sovereignty, dual–use innovation, and responsible information–sharing. The COcyber case studies therefore do not sit apart from global debates; they provide concrete national examples of how these debates materialise in practice. Their value lies precisely in showing that global policy concepts such as “resilience”, “coordination”, “capacity–building” and “civil–military cooperation” become meaningful only when translated into specific legal, institutional, operational and cultural settings.

The comparative analysis confirms that civil–defence cybersecurity cooperation is now a shared strategic priority, but not a uniform implementation challenge. The four country cases point in the same overall direction as the COcyber Needs Assessment: Europe requires stronger coordination, more trusted information–sharing, clearer dual–use pathways, improved skills, more agile innovation mechanisms, and governance structures capable of linking civilian, defence, industrial, academic and policy communities. However, the cases also show that Member States start from different institutional positions and

⁵³ COcyber, D4.2 Slovenia case study, sections 7.1–7.4.

⁵⁴ D2.2 Needs Assessment <https://zenodo.org/records/16760899>

face different pressures. Some need to simplify and connect mature systems; others need to strengthen enforcement, renew strategies, build trust, or compensate for limited scale.

For the final COcyber policy recommendations, this means that the strongest approach is not to prescribe one model, but to propose a common European cooperation framework with adaptable national implementation routes. The recommendations should therefore combine EU-level harmonisation with national flexibility; operational crisis readiness with long-term innovation policy; and technical information-sharing with the political, legal and cultural conditions that make such sharing possible. In the wider global policy context, this positions COcyber as a practical contribution to a larger shift in cybersecurity governance: from fragmented, sector-based protection towards integrated, whole-of-society and internationally connected cyber resilience.

3.7.3 Emerging Policy Ideas from the recommendations

Several policy ideas emerge from the Case studies and are particularly relevant for EU-level reflection.

The first is the move from generalised calls for coordination toward formalised cross-sector governance structures. Rather than limiting cooperation to ad hoc exchanges, the recommendations increasingly favour institutionalised bodies with strategic mandates, decision-making capacity, and links to EU structures. This is significant because it treats coordination as a permanent governance function rather than a temporary project activity.⁵⁵

The second is the recognition that effective information sharing depends on the interaction between formal and informal ecosystems. Spain's recommendation to institutionalise informal professional networks and Slovenia's dual emphasis on formal procedures and informal operational collaboration together point toward a more realistic model of cyber cooperation: one in which trusted informal communities are not displaced, but integrated into validated and accountable structures.⁵⁶

A third is the explicit framing of cybersecurity as an inherently dual-use field requiring lifecycle governance. Spain recommends a long-term industrial policy framework covering the full lifecycle of dual-use cybersecurity technologies, while Slovenia calls for a national strategy for cybersecurity and dual-use research and innovation. These approaches move beyond narrow export-control thinking and instead frame dual-use technologies as part of a larger innovation, industrial, and resilience ecosystem.⁵⁷

⁵⁵ COcyber, D4.2, "Governance structures"; D2.2, sections 3.1.3 and 3.2.2.

⁵⁶ COcyber, D4.2 Spain 7.3; Slovenia 7.3.

⁵⁷ COcyber, D4.2 Spain 7.4; Slovenia 7.4; D4.2, "Support for dual-use technology development".

A fourth idea is the emphasis on integrated capability development through joint training, exchange programmes, joint simulations, crisis-management alignment, and rapid resource reallocation. These measures are important because they create repeated practice, mutual familiarity, and interoperable professional cultures rather than relying solely on formal coordination arrangements.⁵⁸

A fifth is the close integration of innovation policy with cybersecurity resilience. Public procurement for innovation, technology transfer offices, innovation hubs, research incentives, incubation mechanisms, and strategic funding instruments are all treated as instruments of cybersecurity policy rather than peripheral industrial policy tools. This broadens the policy frame and links resilience to competitiveness, industrial capability, and long-term technological autonomy.⁵⁹

3.7.4 Persistent bottlenecks

Despite the breadth and maturity of the cybersecurity ecosystem in each case study, several bottlenecks recur across the cases.

The first bottleneck is governance fragmentation. Spain highlights fragmentation across territorial and institutional levels; Slovenia stresses the absence of sufficiently strategic coordination and the need for a renewed strategy; Hungary points to uneven implementation visibility across sectors; and Lithuania highlights the need for broader and more consistent implementation of cybersecurity policy and law.⁶⁰

The second bottleneck is legal and procedural complexity. Administrative burdens, fragmented rules, rigid intellectual property arrangements, certification delays, export licensing procedures, and uncertainty regarding dual-use governance all slow down technology transfer, information sharing, and operational cooperation. This challenge is especially visible in Spain and Slovenia, but also in Lithuanian and Hungary.⁶¹

The third bottleneck is insufficient trust infrastructure. The Case studies and previously conducted Needs Assessment repeatedly show that information sharing, cooperation between the public and private spheres, and civilian-defence collaboration are weakened where actors lack trusted forums, legal protections, secure channels, and repeated opportunities for interaction. The recommendations on workshops, exchanges,

⁵⁸ COcyber, D2.2, sections 3.1.2, 3.2.1 and 3.2.3.

⁵⁹ COcyber, D2.2, section 3.3.1; D4.2, “Innovation and technology transfer mechanisms” and “Strategic funding and coordination”; Spain 7.2; Slovenia 7.2.

⁶⁰ COcyber, D4.2 Lithuania 7.1; Spain 7.1; Hungary findings on strategy implementation; Slovenia 7.1.

⁶¹ COcyber, D4.2, “Legal and regulatory harmonisation”; Spain 7.1, 7.2 and 7.4; Slovenia 7.2 and 7.4; Lithuania 7.2 and 7.4.

mentorships, common terminology, confidential reporting channels, and cultural exchange in the case studies and needs assessment all respond directly to this problem.⁶²

The fourth bottleneck is limited capacity. Even where laws, strategies, and funding instruments exist, implementation is undermined by shortages of skilled personnel, weak institutional bandwidth, uneven maturity across SMEs and local administrations, and a lack of intermediary structures capable of translating research or policy into practice. This means that capacity gaps constrain the implementation of almost every other recommendation.⁶³

The fifth bottleneck is uneven scale across Europe. Hungary makes this explicit, but it has broader relevance. Smaller Member States may lack the economies of scale required to sustain the full range of capabilities, yet an overly centralised EU approach may reduce local ownership and neglect distributed innovation potential. This tension must be taken seriously when developing EU-wide relevant recommendations.⁶⁴

3.7.5 Foundation for EU-relevant recommendations in cybersecurity

The case studies and Needs Assessment recommendations provide a clear foundation for future EU-relevant recommendations. First, they suggest that the EU's role should be to reduce fragmentation, improve interoperability, support policy learning, and lower the transaction costs of cooperation rather than to replace national responsibility. In other words, the value of EU action lies not in displacing national governance, but in making different national ecosystems work together more coherently.⁶⁵

Second, the work conducted so far by the COcyber project indicates that EU added value is especially strong in domains where national divergence creates direct barriers to cross-border or cross-sector cooperation. These include common standards for information sharing, guidance on dual-use technologies and technology transfer, certification alignment, shared benchmarking, peer learning, joint training, and transnational research and innovation support. In these areas, the EU can provide frameworks, coordination mechanisms, and funding that individual Member States would struggle to deliver alone.⁶⁶

Third, the recommendations underline the importance of differentiated support. Not all Member States begin from the same point in governance maturity, institutional depth, or market scale. EU-level recommendations should therefore enable convergence without

⁶² COcyber, D4.2 Lithuania 7.3; Spain 7.3; Hungary information-sharing findings; Slovenia 7.3; D2.2, sections 3.1.1 and 3.3.2.

⁶³ COcyber, D4.2 Lithuania 7.5; Spain 7.5; Slovenia 7.1 and 7.2; D4.2, "Capacity building and skills development".

⁶⁴ COcyber, D4.2 Hungary case study findings.

⁶⁵ COcyber, D4.2 comparative recommendations.

⁶⁶ COcyber, D4.2, especially "Legal and regulatory harmonisation", "Information sharing ecosystems", "Support for dual-use technology development", and "Strategic funding and coordination".

assuming uniformity. This means creating frameworks that are common enough to foster interoperability but flexible enough to accommodate different administrative traditions, industrial capacities, and security contexts.⁶⁷

Fourth, EU cybersecurity coordination should be built around four interlocking pillars: interoperable governance, trusted information sharing, innovation-enabled resilience, and workforce development. These pillars recur across the cross-cutting and national recommendations and provide a stable architecture for future policy development.⁶⁸

3.8 Thematic categorisation of the recommendations

Given the above mentioned analysis, the following recommendations can be extrapolated. The recommendations can be categorised into ten interrelated thematic domains to help structure the material.

To facilitate visualization the thematic categorisation has been displayed as the table below:

⁶⁷ COcyber, D4.2 comparative recommendations; Hungary findings on scale and smaller Member States.

⁶⁸ COcyber D2.2 and D4.2.

Thematic Area	Main Policy Focus	Purpose	Short-Term Implementation	Medium-Term Implementation	Long-Term Implementation
Governance and institutional coordination	Cross-sector cybersecurity governance involving civilian, defence, public, private, academic, and critical infrastructure actors.	Move cybersecurity cooperation from ad hoc coordination to structured, institutional cooperation.	Map existing national governance structures and identify overlaps, gaps, and unclear mandates. Develop EU guidance on minimum governance functions.	Encourage Member States to establish or strengthen cross-sector cybersecurity bodies with clear mandates, escalation routes, and EU links.	Create a mature EU-wide governance model where national structures are interoperable and regularly connected to EU crisis and policy mechanisms.
Legal and regulatory harmonisation	Reduction of legal fragmentation around dual-use technologies, technology transfer, certification, data sharing, liability, and reporting.	Make cooperation faster, safer, and more predictable across borders and sectors.	Identify the most problematic legal barriers affecting cooperation, reporting, and technology transfer.	Develop EU model clauses, soft-law guidance, and minimum standards for confidential incident reporting and data sharing.	Move toward greater legal convergence across Member States, reducing procedural uncertainty for public and private and civilian-defence cooperation.
Information sharing and trust ecosystems	Trusted information exchange between ISACs, CERTs, CSIRTs, public authorities, private actors, and	Build resilient information-sharing ecosystems that are	Define common information-sharing needs, trusted contact points, confidentiality safeguards, and	Promote interoperable standards such as STIX/TAXII, secure exchange procedures,	Establish a European trust-based information-sharing architecture linking formal mechanisms

	informal professional networks.	trusted, structured, and useful.	feedback expectations.	and validated reporting channels.	with reliable informal networks.
Capacity building, education, and workforce development	Cybersecurity skills, workforce pipelines, joint training, awareness, diversity, and reskilling.	Ensure that policy ambition is matched by human capability and institutional capacity.	Assess priority skills gaps in Member States, SMEs, public administrations, and civil-defence cooperation.	Expand training, vocational programmes, university curricula, and cross-sector learning based on the European Cybersecurity Skills Framework.	Build a sustainable European cybersecurity workforce pipeline capable of supporting public, private, civilian, and defence needs.
Operational readiness, exercises, and crisis response	Joint exercises, simulations, staff exchanges, crisis management frameworks, and emergency mobilisation.	Translate policy coordination into practical interoperability during real incidents.	Develop common exercise scenarios and identify priority actors for joint civilian-defence simulations.	Institutionalise recurring national and EU-supported exercises, staff exchanges, and operational learning mechanisms.	Create a mature European preparedness culture where actors can coordinate rapidly under pressure during large-scale cyber crises.
Innovation, research and technology transfer	R&D incentives, procurement, SME support, technology	Ensure Europe can generate, scale, deploy, and retain	Identify high-potential research outputs and barriers preventing	Strengthen technology transfer offices, incubators,	Build a stronger European cybersecurity

	transfer, and research-to-deployment pathways.	cybersecurity innovation.	deployment commercialisation.	or accelerators, procurement pathways, industry-research partnerships.	innovation ecosystem where research results routinely move into operational use.
Dual-use technologies and civilian-defence integration	Governance of dual-use cybersecurity technologies across research, testing, procurement, deployment, licensing, and export.	Create a coherent framework for using cybersecurity innovation across civilian and defence applications.	Clarify definitions, criteria, and practical challenges related to dual-use cybersecurity technologies.	Develop EU guidance and cooperation models linking civilian cybersecurity initiatives with defence innovation frameworks.	Establish a lifecycle-based EU approach to dual-use cyber innovation, covering development, transfer, deployment, and oversight.
Strategic funding scaling, and European coordination	Alignment of Digital Europe, Horizon Europe, EDF, EDA related instruments and other cybersecurity funding streams.	Improve strategic coherence, reduce duplication, support capability development across Europe.	Map funding overlaps, gaps, and barriers that prevent projects from moving from pilot to deployment.	Improve coordination between funding instruments and create clearer scale-up pathways for promising cybersecurity solutions.	Develop a more integrated EU funding ecosystem that supports shared capabilities, cross-border platforms, and balanced participation by smaller Member States.
Hybrid threats resilience, and	Integration of cyber policy with hybrid	Reflect the reality that cybersecurity is part	Identify where cyber risks intersect with	Link cybersecurity planning more	Embed cybersecurity within a broader

<p>strategic preparedness</p>	<p>threats, disinformation, strategic dependencies, economic coercion, and crisis preparedness.</p>	<p>of a wider resilience and security agenda.</p>	<p>hybrid geopolitical exposure, and dependencies.</p>	<p>threats, systematically with EU resilience, crisis-management, and security frameworks.</p>	<p>European strategic preparedness model, especially for Member States facing heightened geopolitical risks.</p>
<p>Monitoring, evaluation and policy learning</p>	<p>Indicators, benchmarking, peer review, dissemination of lessons learned, and continuous policy adaptation.</p>	<p>Ensure cybersecurity policy evolves through evidence, comparison, and feedback.</p>	<p>Define common indicators and evaluation criteria for EU-supported cybersecurity initiatives.</p>	<p>Introduce peer review, benchmarking, mutual learning, and structured dissemination of good practices.</p>	<p>Create a continuous policy-learning cycle where cybersecurity governance is regularly updated based on evidence and operational experience.</p>

Table 2 Thematic categorisation

4 Preliminary Policy Recommendations

1. Establish an EU framework for cross-sector cybersecurity governance

Priority: Very High

The EU should promote a common governance model requiring Member States to institutionalise cross-sector cybersecurity coordination bodies involving civilian authorities, defence actors, industry, academia, critical infrastructure operators, and relevant regulatory bodies. These structures should have clearly defined mandates for strategic planning, crisis escalation, information-sharing coordination, civil-defence alignment, and liaison with EU-level mechanisms.

Short-term implementation steps

- Develop EU-level guidance defining minimum functions for national cross-sector cybersecurity coordination bodies.
- Encourage Member States to designate clear national contact points for civilian-defence cybersecurity coordination.
- Use existing EU platforms and networks to test common governance principles.

Medium-term implementation steps

- Support Member States in creating or adapting national coordination bodies with cross-sector mandates.
- Establish regular EU-level coordination meetings between national bodies.
- Develop shared procedures for escalation, crisis communication, and coordination during major cyber incidents.
- Link national governance bodies more clearly with CSIRTs, CERTs, defence cyber commands, regulators, and critical infrastructure authorities.

Long-term implementation steps

- Move toward a mature EU-wide governance ecosystem where national structures are interoperable.
- Embed cross-sector governance requirements into EU cybersecurity funding and policy programmes.

- Conduct periodic peer reviews of Member State governance models.
- Create a standing EU-level forum for civilian–defence cybersecurity policy coordination.

Possible implementation challenges

- Member State sensitivity around national security and defence competences.
- Uneven institutional maturity across Member States.
- Risk of duplicating existing structures rather than improving coordination.
- Difficulty involving private-sector and defence actors in the same governance space.

2. Reduce legal fragmentation through EU guidance on dual-use and technology transfer

Priority: Very High

The European Commission should issue practical guidance, model clauses, and soft-law instruments to clarify how cybersecurity technologies with civilian and defence relevance should be developed, transferred, commercialised, procured, and deployed across the EU. This should reduce uncertainty around licensing, certification, export controls, intellectual property, procurement rules, and compliance obligations.

Short-term implementation steps

- Identify the main legal barriers affecting cybersecurity technology transfer and dual-use innovation.
- Produce practical EU guidance explaining how existing rules apply to dual-use cyber tools.
- Develop model contractual clauses for research consortia, SMEs, universities, and public buyers.
- Clarify how EU-funded cybersecurity research can transition toward operational use.

Medium-term implementation steps

- Create a voluntary EU legal guidance toolkit for dual-use cybersecurity projects.
- Promote common terminology for dual-use cyber technologies across EU programmes.
- Support national authorities in applying guidance consistently.
- Encourage legal helpdesks or advisory services for SMEs and research organisations.

Long-term implementation steps

- Assess whether soft-law guidance is sufficient or whether more formal legal instruments are needed.
- Harmonise technology transfer practices across Member States where possible.
- Link legal guidance to procurement, certification, and funding frameworks.
- Build a predictable legal pathway from research to deployment.

Possible implementation challenges

- Divergent national rules and interpretations.
- Sensitivity around export controls and defence-related technologies.
- Legal uncertainty for SMEs and universities.
- Risk that guidance remains too general to be operationally useful.

3. Build a European trust-based information-sharing architecture

Priority: Very High

The EU should support a more coherent information-sharing ecosystem by encouraging all Member States to establish or strengthen national ISACs or equivalent trusted communities with cross-sector mandates. These should be linked to CERTs, CSIRTs, sectoral regulators, critical infrastructure actors, and, where appropriate, defence stakeholders. At EU level, common protocols, secure platforms, confidentiality safeguards, and interoperable threat-intelligence formats should be promoted.

Short-term implementation steps

- Map existing ISACs, sectoral information-sharing structures, and national cyber communities.
- Identify sectors and Member States where trusted sharing mechanisms are weak or absent.
- Promote minimum principles for trust-based cyber information sharing.
- Encourage use of common threat-intelligence formats such as STIX/TAXII.

Medium-term implementation steps

- Support the creation or strengthening of national and sectoral ISACs.
- Develop EU-level interoperability guidelines for cyber threat intelligence exchange.
- Establish secure channels for cross-border and cross-sector sharing.
- Define procedures for anonymisation, confidentiality, and controlled dissemination.

Long-term implementation steps

- Create a mature EU information-sharing architecture linking national, sectoral, and EU-level structures.
- Enable structured exchange between civilian and defence-relevant cybersecurity communities where appropriate.
- Integrate information-sharing mechanisms into exercises and crisis-management procedures.
- Evaluate whether shared platforms or federated information-sharing systems are needed.

Possible implementation challenges

- Low trust between public and private actors.
- Fear of reputational damage or regulatory exposure.
- Technical interoperability gaps.
- Different levels of maturity among Member States and sectors.

4. Create EU standards for protected cyber incident reporting

Priority: Very High

The EU should develop minimum principles for confidential, legally protected, and operationally useful cyber incident reporting channels. These should be designed to encourage timely reporting by private-sector actors, operators of essential services, SMEs, and public authorities, while ensuring that reporting entities receive actionable feedback.

Short-term implementation steps

- Review existing reporting obligations under EU and national frameworks.
- Identify where fear of liability, reputational damage, or unclear procedures discourages reporting.
- Develop minimum EU principles for confidential and protected reporting.
- Define what feedback reporting entities should receive in return.

Medium-term implementation steps

- Encourage Member States to create or adapt protected reporting channels.
- Develop standardised reporting templates and escalation pathways.
- Establish safeguards for sensitive commercial and security information.

- Link incident reporting to national CSIRTs, regulators, and information-sharing communities.

Long-term implementation steps

- Build an EU-wide culture of trusted and timely incident reporting.
- Use anonymised reporting data to improve strategic threat analysis.
- Integrate reporting outputs into EU-level risk assessments and policy learning.
- Periodically review whether protections are sufficient to incentivise reporting.

Possible implementation challenges

- Tension between regulatory enforcement and trust-building.
- Concerns from companies about legal liability and public disclosure.
- Duplication with existing reporting obligations.
- Difficulty ensuring that reporting leads to useful feedback.

5. Make cybersecurity skills a strategic EU capability priority

Priority: High

The EU should treat the cybersecurity workforce gap as a structural resilience challenge and support Member States in building long-term national skills pipelines aligned with the European Cybersecurity Skills Framework. This should include vocational training, university curricula, joint certifications, reskilling schemes, lifelong learning, early cyber education, and targeted support for less-resourced Member States.

Short-term implementation steps

- Map cybersecurity skills shortages across Member States and sectors.
- Identify urgent workforce gaps in public administration, defence, critical infrastructure, and SMEs.
- Promote common training modules aligned with existing EU skills frameworks.
- Fund short reskilling and upskilling programmes for high-need sectors.

Medium-term implementation steps

- Support national cybersecurity education strategies.
- Develop joint civilian–defence training modules.
- Expand cyber curricula in vocational schools and universities.
- Create EU-supported certification pathways recognised across Member States.

Long-term implementation steps

- Establish sustainable national cyber talent pipelines.
- Integrate cybersecurity awareness and digital resilience into early education.
- Create mobility and exchange schemes for cyber professionals.
- Reduce skills asymmetries between larger and smaller Member States.

Possible implementation challenges

- Competition with private-sector salaries.
- Difficulty retaining cyber experts in public institutions.
- Uneven education and training capacity across Member States.
- Fragmented certification systems.

6. Institutionalise joint civilian–defence training and exercises across Europe

Priority: High

The EU should expand support for regular joint cybersecurity exercises, simulations, staff exchanges, and secondments involving civilian authorities, defence actors, academia, industry, and critical infrastructure operators. These activities should build operational readiness, trust, shared procedures, and a common professional language across sectors.

Short-term implementation steps

- Map existing EU and national cyber exercises involving civilian and defence actors.
- Identify gaps in participation, scenarios, and coordination mechanisms.
- Develop model exercise scenarios covering cross-sector cyber crises.
- Encourage Member States to include private-sector and critical infrastructure actors in exercises.

Medium-term implementation steps

- Create recurring EU-supported civilian–defence cyber exercise programmes.
- Introduce staff exchanges and short-term secondments between relevant institutions.
- Link exercises to national crisis-management structures.
- Use exercises to test incident reporting, escalation, and information-sharing procedures.

Long-term implementation steps

- Institutionalise regular cross-sector exercises across all Member States.

- Develop advanced simulations involving hybrid threats, supply-chain attacks, and cross-border incidents.
- Use exercise outcomes to update policy, governance, and operational procedures.
- Build a European community of practice for civilian-defence cyber preparedness.

Possible implementation challenges

- Classification and confidentiality barriers.
- Cultural differences between civilian and defence communities.
- Limited resources for smaller Member States.
- Difficulty translating exercise lessons into policy change.

7. Develop an EU approach to dual-use cybersecurity innovation

Priority: Medium-High

The EU should adopt a dedicated policy approach for dual-use cybersecurity technologies covering the full innovation lifecycle: research, testing, validation, procurement, deployment, licensing, export controls, supply chains, and scaling. This should create clearer pathways for technologies with both civilian and defence relevance.

Short-term implementation steps

- Define practical criteria for identifying dual-use cybersecurity technologies.
- Map where dual-use cyber innovation is currently supported by EU programmes.
- Identify gaps between civilian cybersecurity funding and defence innovation instruments.
- Provide guidance for developers, SMEs, and research organisations.

Medium-term implementation steps

- Create pilot schemes for dual-use cybersecurity innovation.
- Align relevant civilian and defence funding calls where appropriate.
- Support testing and validation environments for dual-use cyber tools.
- Encourage demand-driven procurement involving public authorities and end-users.

Long-term implementation steps

- Establish a coherent EU dual-use cyber innovation pathway from research to deployment.
- Support cross-border dual-use cybersecurity projects.

- Link innovation funding to procurement and operational uptake.
- Develop safeguards to ensure responsible and legally compliant deployment.

Possible implementation challenges

- Unclear boundaries between civilian, security, and defence applications.
- Export-control and licensing complexity.
- Risk aversion among public buyers.
- Difficulty involving SMEs in defence-relevant markets.

8. Strengthen European cybersecurity innovation ecosystems

Priority: Medium

The EU should expand support for cybersecurity R&D incentives, innovation hubs, technology transfer structures, procurement instruments, and market-access mechanisms. Particular attention should be given to SMEs, universities, research centres, technology transfer offices, incubators, accelerators, and demand-driven procurement.

Short-term implementation steps

- Identify cybersecurity innovation gaps in Member States and regions.
- Map existing innovation hubs, competence centres, accelerators, and TTOs.
- Provide targeted support to SMEs and research organisations seeking commercialisation.
- Encourage public buyers to define cybersecurity capability needs more clearly.

Medium-term implementation steps

- Expand cybersecurity-specific incubators and accelerators.
- Support technology transfer offices in cyber-related commercialisation.
- Develop procurement pathways for innovative cybersecurity solutions.
- Encourage cross-border innovation consortia involving SMEs, academia, and public authorities.

Long-term implementation steps

- Build a more integrated European cybersecurity innovation market.
- Improve the transition from research outputs to deployable solutions.
- Strengthen Europe's strategic technological autonomy in cybersecurity.
- Support long-term scaling of successful cyber solutions across Member States.

Possible implementation challenges

- Fragmented market demand.
- Limited procurement expertise in public authorities.
- Administrative burden for SMEs.
- Weak links between research, end-users, and buyers.

9. Ensure smaller Member States benefit from EU scaling without being marginalised

Priority: Medium

EU cybersecurity policy should account for differences in national size, capability, market maturity, and institutional capacity. EU programmes should allow smaller Member States to access shared capabilities, participate in transnational projects, benefit from common platforms, and contribute their own innovation potential without being overshadowed by larger Member States.

Short-term implementation steps

- Identify capability and market gaps affecting smaller Member States.
- Ensure EU calls and programmes include accessibility criteria for smaller ecosystems.
- Promote participation of smaller Member States in transnational consortia.
- Provide administrative support for less-resourced applicants.

Medium-term implementation steps

- Create targeted capacity-building measures for smaller Member States.
- Support shared cybersecurity services, platforms, and testing facilities.
- Encourage partnerships between larger and smaller Member State ecosystems.
- Ensure smaller Member States are represented in governance and peer-learning structures.

Long-term implementation steps

- Develop a balanced European cybersecurity ecosystem with distributed capabilities.
- Prevent over-concentration of funding and expertise in a small number of countries.
- Enable smaller Member States to specialise in niche areas of cybersecurity excellence.
- Use EU-level scaling to reduce, rather than reinforce, capability gaps.

Possible implementation challenges

- Unequal administrative capacity to access EU funding.
- Concentration of expertise in larger Member States.
- Smaller markets may struggle to sustain cyber companies.
- Risk of symbolic participation without meaningful influence.

10. Integrate hybrid–threat preparedness more explicitly into EU cybersecurity policy

Priority: High

The EU should integrate hybrid–threat preparedness more explicitly into cybersecurity coordination, recognising that cyber incidents increasingly intersect with disinformation, economic coercion, strategic dependencies, foreign interference, and wider security tensions. Cybersecurity policy should therefore be linked more closely with resilience, crisis management, strategic communication, and security preparedness frameworks.

Short-term implementation steps

- Map where hybrid threats are already addressed in EU and national cybersecurity strategies.
- Identify gaps between cybersecurity, crisis management, disinformation response, and resilience policies.
- Develop cyber–hybrid threat scenarios for policy exercises.
- Encourage Member States to include hybrid–threat dimensions in cybersecurity risk assessments.

Medium-term implementation steps

- Integrate hybrid–threat scenarios into joint civilian–defence cyber exercises.
- Strengthen links between cybersecurity authorities, strategic communication actors, law enforcement, defence, and crisis–management bodies.
- Develop guidance on responding to cyber incidents with hybrid characteristics.
- Encourage cross–border exchange of lessons learned from Member States with high exposure to hybrid threats.

Long-term implementation steps

- Establish a more integrated EU approach to cyber and hybrid resilience.
- Embed hybrid–threat preparedness into national cybersecurity strategies.
- Use cyber–hybrid analysis to inform EU risk assessments and preparedness planning.

- Strengthen Europe’s capacity to detect, attribute, communicate, and respond to complex cyber-enabled threats.

Possible implementation challenges

- Institutional silos between cyber, defence, intelligence, crisis management, and communication actors.
- Sensitivity around attribution and intelligence-sharing.
- Different threat perceptions among Member States.
- Risk of expanding cybersecurity policy too broadly without clear responsibilities.

11. Improve alignment of EU funding instruments

Priority: High

The EU should improve strategic alignment between cybersecurity funding under Digital Europe, Horizon Europe, the European Defence Fund, EDA-linked mechanisms, and other relevant instruments. The objective should be to reduce duplication, make civilian–defence pathways more navigable, and help projects move from research and pilots toward deployment and long-term sustainability.

Short-term implementation steps

- Map existing EU cybersecurity funding instruments and identify overlaps.
- Produce clear guidance showing how projects can move between research, innovation, deployment, and defence-relevant funding.
- Identify gaps where promising projects fail to progress after pilot stages.
- Encourage coordination between EU funding bodies and programme managers.

Medium-term implementation steps

- Create more coherent funding pathways for cross-border and dual-use cyber projects.
- Align selected calls across civilian and defence-relevant instruments where legally appropriate.
- Introduce stronger sustainability and exploitation requirements in funded projects.
- Support project matchmaking between SMEs, research actors, public authorities, and defence stakeholders.

Long-term implementation steps

- Build an integrated EU funding pipeline for cybersecurity capability development.

- Reduce fragmentation between research, innovation, procurement, and deployment funding.
- Use funding strategically to support EU cyber resilience and technological autonomy.
- Establish mechanisms to scale successful pilot projects across Member States.

Possible implementation challenges

- Different legal bases and objectives of EU funding instruments.
- Administrative complexity for applicants.
- Risk of duplication between programmes.
- Difficulty bridging the gap between research outputs and operational procurement.

12. Embed monitoring, peer review, and policy learning in EU cybersecurity initiatives

Priority: Medium

All major EU-supported cybersecurity initiatives should include measurable monitoring and evaluation frameworks, combining qualitative and quantitative indicators. At EU level, this should be complemented by peer reviews, benchmarking, structured dissemination of lessons learned, and regular policy updates. This is especially important in governance, information sharing, dual-use innovation, technology transfer, skills, and incident reporting.

Short-term implementation steps

- Define core indicators for EU-supported cybersecurity initiatives.
- Require major projects and programmes to include monitoring and learning plans.
- Identify good practices from existing national and EU cybersecurity initiatives.
- Develop templates for lessons learned, peer review, and policy feedback.

Medium-term implementation steps

- Establish periodic peer reviews among Member States.
- Create benchmarking tools for governance, information sharing, skills, and innovation maturity.
- Disseminate successful practices through EU-level communities and platforms.
- Use monitoring findings to adjust funding priorities and policy guidance.

Long-term implementation steps

- Create a continuous EU cybersecurity policy-learning cycle.

- Institutionalise benchmarking and peer review across major cybersecurity initiatives.
- Use evidence from monitoring to update strategies, guidance, and funding priorities.
- Ensure that EU cybersecurity policy evolves with changing threats, technologies, and operational needs.

Possible implementation challenges

- Difficulty defining comparable indicators across Member States.
- Risk of reporting becoming a bureaucratic exercise.
- Uneven data availability.
- Political sensitivity around benchmarking national performance.

5 Validation processes

The COcyber policy work was validated through a structured series of four policy-oriented workshops involving members of the COcyber Community and stakeholders from relevant likeminded projects in the field of cybersecurity. This validation process formed a central part of the participatory methodology of Deliverable 4.5, ensuring that the recommendations were not only based on desk research and national case-study findings, but also tested against the practical experience, expectations, and concerns of the wider COcyber Community.

5.1 Validation by the COcyber Community through four Policy-Oriented Workshops

The four policy-oriented workshops were designed as successive validation steps rather than isolated consultation events. Each workshop focused on a different stage of the policy development process: validating the policy and literature review, testing the relevance of the national case-study findings, assessing the preliminary recommendations, and refining the final policy package. The discussions held in each workshop and the Mentimeter polling provided an additional layer of evidence by capturing participants' immediate priorities, concerns, and perceptions of feasibility.

COcyber Policy-Oriented workshop: Validating Europe's current Civilian-Defence Cybersecurity policy Landscape

The first workshop focused on whether the policy and literature review had correctly identified the main gaps affecting civil–defence cybersecurity cooperation in Europe. 11 Participants, representing a balanced mix of cybersecurity industry, EU–level institutional expertise, standardisation, academia, resilience policy, and SME representation, coming from organisations such as **eShard**, **28 Digital**, **Agoria**, **Sciences Po**, the **Euro–Atlantic Resilience Centre**, **ENISA**, **ISO**, and the **European DIGITAL SME Alliance**, broadly confirmed that the review was accurate and well–grounded, especially in its legal and institutional framing. The feedback recognised that the review correctly identifies a core structural challenge: civilian cybersecurity is primarily developed through EU internal–market, resilience and regulatory instruments, while defence and national security remain largely Member State responsibilities. This distinction provides an important basis for explaining why civilian–defence cyber coordination is necessary, but also politically and institutionally difficult.

Participants also confirmed that the review was strong in showing that civilian–defence cybersecurity cooperation is no longer only a strategic aspiration. The review successfully connected the EU Cybersecurity Strategy, the Strategic Compass, the EU Policy on Cyber Defence, NATO–related developments, ENISA threat assessments and EU crisis–management mechanisms to a broader policy shift in which civilian infrastructure, defence readiness, cyber resilience, technological sovereignty and crisis response are increasingly interdependent.

At the same time, the workshop feedback showed that the review needed to move beyond policy mapping and provide sharper operational conclusions. Participants stressed that the key challenge is not simply the existence of many EU and national instruments, but the practical question of who acts, through which mechanism, under which authority, and with what legal safeguards during a cyber crisis.

The workshop also highlighted operational civilian–defence information sharing as a central policy gap. Participants underlined the need for minimum shareable information categories, trusted contact points, secure communication channels, escalation procedures, feedback loops and clear rules for handling sensitive or classified information. This feedback strengthened the rationale for making trusted information sharing one of the core pillars of the final recommendations.

A further important issue raised during the workshop was the mobilisation of civilian cybersecurity expertise during crises, hybrid escalation or armed conflict. Participants considered this an urgent but underdeveloped area of EU policy. The discussion showed that civilian experts, ethical hackers, private providers, reservists and cyber volunteers can contribute to resilience, but only if their role is governed by clear legal, operational and accountability safeguards. The feedback therefore justified giving more explicit attention to pre–vetted expert pools, cyber reserve mechanisms, liability rules, codes of conduct, reporting channels and a clear separation between defensive civilian support and uncontrolled offensive cyber activity.

The polling showed that participants considered **role clarity and escalation across crisis coordination channels** to be the most urgent gap when the issues were ranked against each other. This indicates that stakeholders did not see the main problem only as a lack of cooperation, but as a lack of clearly defined procedures, responsibilities, and escalation routes during crises.

Figure 1 Gaps by urgency

At the same time, the polling also highlighted the **mobilisation of the civilian cybersecurity talent pool during conflict, including war**, as an issue requiring urgent policy attention. This is significant because it points to a gap that is less developed in current EU cybersecurity policy: the role, status, governance, and limits of civilian cyber contributors, cyber volunteers, reservists, or private-sector experts during periods of conflict or major crisis. Participants therefore pushed the analysis beyond ordinary cyber preparedness and towards the more sensitive question of how civilian capabilities could be used lawfully, safely, and effectively in crisis or conflict situations.

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Which gaps most urgently require policy action in the next 12 months?

Figure 2 Gaps requiring policy action

The open responses reinforced this interpretation. Participants asked for a clearer institutional and procedural pathway for cooperation, clarification of national crisis roles and responsibilities, and greater attention to the consequences of unsatisfactory cooperation. One response also referred to the need to simplify access to senior cyber reservists in national crisis situations, which suggests that civil–defence cooperation should not only be discussed at a strategic level, but also in terms of practical activation mechanisms.

Overall, Workshop 1 strengthened the policy and literature review by confirming its analytical foundations while also clarifying its main improvement need. The review should not only describe the existing policy landscape; it should identify the operational pathways through which civilian and defence actors can cooperate in practice, while respecting Member State competences, national–security sensitivities, democratic oversight, proportionality and data–protection safeguards. The feedback confirmed that the most important missing element was not another general call for coordination. Rather, the review needed to place stronger emphasis on **who acts, through which procedure, under which authority, and with what legal safeguards** during cyber crises. It also justified adding a more explicit discussion of civilian cyber mobilisation in conflict–related contexts.

COcyber Policy–Oriented workshop: Integration of COcyber Case study Findings

The second workshop tested whether the case-study findings from Lithuania, Hungary, Spain, and Slovenia reflected wider European challenges. 15 participants, representing a wide range of sectors, including EU and international policy, cybersecurity and digital industry, telecommunications, geospatial and maritime security, academia and research, agri-food/critical-sector industry, EU external action, and civil security, stemming from **organisations**, such as, **Lisbon Council, 4iG Nyrt, IVSZ Hungarian Association of Digital Companies, International Community for Georgia Development and Progress, Nokia, SafeMarine, Molino Cañuelas SACIFIA, EEAS, Sciences Po, and Engineering**, confirmed that these findings were robust and realistic as problem-pattern evidence, although not as a fully representative assessment of all 27 Member States. This distinction is important: the case studies should not be presented as a complete EU-wide mapping exercise, but as a set of national examples that reveal recurring governance, trust, capacity and implementation challenges across different institutional contexts.

Participants considered the findings realistic because they did not assume that civilian-defence cybersecurity cooperation can be addressed through one uniform model. The countries examined start from different legal, institutional, operational and geopolitical positions. Spain reflects the challenge of coordinating a complex and mature ecosystem; Lithuania highlights security-driven resilience, hybrid-threat awareness and skills; Hungary underlines trust, language and scale-related constraints; and Slovenia points to the importance of strategy renewal and institutional accountability. The diversity of these cases helped demonstrate that EU-level action should support convergence and interoperability without replacing national flexibility.

The polling and discussions showed that participants were relatively familiar with civilian-defence cybersecurity cooperation, which strengthens the relevance of their feedback. When asked which finding felt most accurate across Europe, the strongest response was that **information sharing is limited by trust gaps**. The second most important issue was that **technology transfer remains fragmented**.

Figure 3 Finding accuracy

This result is important because it confirms that the case studies should not be interpreted only as four separate national experiences. Instead, they point to broader European problems: trust deficits, legal uncertainty, weak cross-sector coordination, and fragmented pathways between research, innovation, and operational use. The workshop therefore helped connect the national findings to a wider EU-level policy agenda.

The polling also showed that participants considered **legal and regulatory fragmentation** and **civilian-defence trust-building** to be underemphasised in the findings. This feedback helped sharpen the final recommendations by showing that formal rules and informal trust must be considered together. Legal frameworks, classification rules, procurement procedures and technology-transfer requirements shape what actors are allowed to share, while trust determines whether they are willing to share in practice. Similarly, information-sharing systems must not be one-way reporting mechanisms; they need feedback loops so that companies, SMEs, critical infrastructure operators and other contributors receive useful information in return.

Figure 4 Underemphasized issues

The governance-related polling produced a similar message. Participants ranked **better coordination between national and EU levels** as the most important governance priority, followed by better implementation of existing strategies and stronger national cross-sector governance bodies. This indicates that the problem is not simply the absence of strategies or institutions. Rather, stakeholders see a gap between existing policy frameworks and their practical implementation across governance levels.

Figure 5 Most important governance priorities

The polling on governance weaknesses also identified the **lack of feedback mechanisms** as the most important weakness, followed by weak coordination across sectors and limited political prioritisation. This is an important analytical finding. It suggests that stakeholders want cooperation systems that are not only consultative, but also iterative: information should circulate back to those who provide it, lessons should be captured, and policy frameworks should be updated based on operational experience.

Figure 6 Biggest governance weakness

Overall, Workshop 2 strengthened the analysis by showing that the country case studies should be framed around three cross-cutting European challenges: **trust-based information sharing, EU–national coordination, and the implementation gap between policy commitments and operational practice.**

COcyber Policy–Oriented workshop: Preliminary Policy Recommendations

The third workshop focused on the preliminary COcyber policy recommendations. Participants broadly confirmed the relevance of the recommendations, but also indicated that they needed to become more practical, more clearly sequenced and more explicit about implementation responsibilities.

A key finding was that the recommendation on building a European trust-based information-sharing architecture was already well grounded in existing policy and

operational practice. Participants noted that it builds on existing mechanisms such as ISACs, CERTs/CSIRTs, sectoral cyber communities and common threat-intelligence formats such as STIX/TAXII. This means the recommendation does not require creating an entirely new model from scratch; rather, it seeks to connect, scale and make interoperable practices that already exist unevenly across Europe.

At the same time, 11 participants covering several relevant sectors, including private consultancy and cybersecurity expertise, civil security and industry representation, maritime security, EU external and security policy, national defence, and public-sector digital governance, and coming from organisations such as **GNKS Consult BV**, **SafeMarine**, **EEAS**, the **Ministry of Defense of Lithuania**, the **State Digital Solutions Agency**, and **URSIV**, warned that the recommendation on establishing an EU framework for cross-sector cybersecurity governance risks overgeneralising across Member States. While the idea is valid, a common governance model will look different in federal, centralised, large, small, highly mature or less mature national systems. It also touches sensitive areas of national security and defence competence. This feedback helped refine the recommendation so that it is framed around common functions, coordination principles, interoperability and national contact points, rather than a single institutional blueprint imposed across all Member States.

The discussion also revealed that the recommendations look different depending on the stakeholder perspective. From a government perspective, formal coordination structures may raise mandate and competence questions. From a defence perspective, classification, intelligence-sharing and operational-security limits are central. From an industry perspective, protected reporting and information sharing remain risky unless confidentiality, liability protection and feedback mechanisms are credible. From an academic and research perspective, dual-use innovation may raise concerns about export controls, intellectual property, publication freedom and unclear pathways from research to deployment. This confirmed the need for the final recommendations to recognise different incentives, risks and constraints across the civilian, defence, industry and research communities.

Participants identified the recommendation on developing an EU approach to dual-use cybersecurity innovation as conceptually sound but difficult to implement. The recommendation correctly addresses the full lifecycle from research, testing and procurement to deployment, licensing, export controls, supply chains and scaling. However, it faces major barriers because dual-use cyber tools sit between civilian, security, defence, commercial and export-control regimes. This feedback showed that the final recommendation needed more precision: it should clarify whether its main focus is legal guidance, technology transfer, procurement, certification, SME participation, funding alignment or lifecycle governance.

Another important finding was that several recommendations lacked clear institutional ownership. Participants stressed that each recommendation should specify a lead actor,

supporting actors, decision pathway and short-term implementation step. For example, Member States should retain ownership of national governance structures; ENISA, CSIRTs and relevant EU cyber structures could support information-sharing and incident-reporting measures; the European Commission, ECCC and relevant programme managers should play a central role in funding alignment; and defence-related actors should be involved where national security, hybrid-threat or dual-use implications are present.

When participants were asked which recommendations would deliver the greatest European added value in the next two to three years, the strongest candidates were trust-based information sharing, protected incident reporting and funding alignment. These areas can generate practical value relatively quickly because they can begin through mapping, guidance, templates, interoperability principles and better coordination of existing mechanisms, without requiring major treaty-level or competence changes.

The Mentimeter word cloud showed that **trust** was the dominant perceived obstacle to effective civilian-defence cyber coordination in Europe, accompanied by related terms such as fragmentation, standardisation, lack of confidence, and trust framework. This reinforced one of the central messages of the recommendations: technical platforms and formal structures are not sufficient unless they are supported by trusted relationships, clear procedures, and safeguards for sensitive information.

Figure 7 Biggest obstacles

When participants were asked which area most urgently needed EU action, the strongest responses were **trusted information sharing** and **skills and workforce**. This indicates that stakeholders viewed cooperation and capability-building as mutually dependent. Information-sharing frameworks cannot function without skilled actors who understand

what can be shared, how it should be protected, and how it can be translated into operational value.

The polling also showed that participants considered the preliminary recommendations only moderately reflective of operational reality, with an average score of **3.1 out of 5**. This is an important finding because it suggests that the recommendations were broadly relevant, but still needed to become more practical and implementation-oriented. In other words, the workshop did not reject the direction of the recommendations, but indicated that they required clearer operational pathways, responsible actors, and implementation steps.

Figure 8 Operational reality

The most underestimated implementation barriers identified were **classification and sensitivity constraints** and **weak interoperability between systems and institutions**. This suggests that the recommendations needed to address not only political willingness, but also the concrete conditions under which cooperation can take place. Sensitive information cannot be shared unless actors have confidence in classification handling, access controls, secure channels, and agreed procedures.

When participants ranked actions for the next two to three years, **trust-based information sharing** came first, followed by a governance framework and protected incident reporting. This ranking shows that information sharing should be treated as a central pillar of the recommendations, not as a secondary technical issue. It also indicates that governance, incident reporting, and information sharing should be connected rather than developed separately.

Figure 9 Ranked by urgency

The open responses identified some missing or underdeveloped elements. Participants suggested a stronger interface for sharing useful information and capabilities across domains, while recognising that not everything can or should be shared. Some also raised the idea of more centralised civilian–military cyber coordination structures. Even if such proposals may be politically sensitive, they show that stakeholders are looking for clearer operational interfaces between civilian and defence communities.

Overall, Workshop 3 led to an important refinement of the recommendations. It showed that the final policy package should move from broad thematic recommendations towards **implementation pathways**, especially for trusted information sharing, protected reporting, skills development, and governance coordination.

COcyber Policy–Oriented workshop: Final Policy Recommendations

The fourth workshop focused on final validation, prioritisation and refinement of the COcyber policy recommendations. Participants expressed strong overall support for the policy direction, confirming that the recommendations address important EU cybersecurity coordination gaps and are relevant to both civilian and defence cybersecurity communities. However, the feedback also showed that realism, precision and implementation detail remained the areas requiring the most attention.

This distinction is analytically important. 15 Participants covering a broad range of sectors, including cybersecurity and digital services, civil security and project coordination, EU institutional and external action expertise, legal and regulatory expertise, academia and

research, law enforcement, digital trust services, consultancy, and industry/SME, coming from **GuardedBox, Jones Day, ENISA, EEAS, Ghent University, the Federal Judicial Police Belgium, Cyberecocol Global Services, trustilio, IVSZ / Hungarian Association of Digital Companies, Accenture, and 28 Digital**, broadly agreed with the policy direction, but they still saw a need for more precise wording, clearer division of responsibilities, and more realistic sequencing. The final recommendations should therefore avoid being presented as a list of ambitions. They should instead indicate which actions can be taken in the short term, which require medium-term institutional development, and which depend on longer-term legal or political change.

A central conclusion from the governance discussion was that the proposed arrangements are realistic only if they are framed as coordination, guidance, interoperability and capacity-building measures, rather than as an attempt to centralise national cybersecurity or defence decision-making at the EU level. Participants confirmed that Member States remain sensitive about national security, defence competences, classification rules and operational control. Therefore, the EU's added value lies in defining common governance principles, supporting peer learning, aligning funding, encouraging national contact points, promoting shared procedures and linking national structures to EU-level mechanisms.

The workshop also reinforced the importance of clear interfaces rather than merged mandates. Civilian and defence actors can coordinate through liaison officers, controlled information-sharing channels, joint exercises, escalation thresholds, anonymised or sanitised threat intelligence, and scenario-based planning. Defence actors should be involved where incidents have national security, hybrid-threat, critical infrastructure or dual-use implications, while operational command, classified intelligence and military decision-making should remain with the competent national authorities.

On information sharing, participants stressed that the system must be trusted, protected and operationally useful. Voluntary reporting alone may not be sufficient for private-sector participation unless combined with credible incentives, confidentiality protections, anonymisation, controlled dissemination, legal safeguards and useful feedback. Participants also noted that technical data is often less sensitive than the contextual analysis surrounding an incident. This means that over-processing or over-classifying information can reduce its operational value, because threat intelligence becomes less useful as time passes. The final recommendations should therefore emphasise rapid classification, timely sanitisation and practical feedback loops.

The fourth workshop also highlighted the need for a common language and common terminology. Participants noted that the EU has policies and strategies, but still lacks a sufficiently shared operational vocabulary and doctrine across Member States and stakeholder communities. This is relevant not only for translation across languages, but also for ensuring that civilian authorities, defence actors, industry, SMEs and research organisations understand concepts such as incident reporting, escalation, dual-use,

protected sharing, cyber reserve, operational readiness and strategic autonomy in the same way. This feedback supports the inclusion of common terminology as either a cross-cutting implementation requirement or a distinct policy action.

The capability and funding discussion confirmed that civil–defence cybersecurity capacity should be treated as a full lifecycle: identifying needs, funding research, validating tools, supporting SMEs, training users, running exercises, procuring solutions, monitoring outcomes and updating policy. Participants stressed that interoperability and resilience require action at strategic, tactical, operational and technical levels. They also highlighted that operational–level competence is often weaker than strategic ambition, meaning that skills, exercises and practical procedures are essential. Training and exercises, including civilian–military cyber exercises, cyber ranges, red–team/blue–team formats, cyber reserve models and lessons–learned mechanisms, should therefore be more clearly reflected in the final recommendations.

The workshop also helped refine the sovereignty and strategic autonomy dimension of the recommendations. Participants underlined that sovereignty should not remain rhetorical. It should be translated into practical tools such as dependency mapping, trusted procurement requirements, certification links, investment priorities, supply–chain assurance, secure cloud and infrastructure choices, and monitoring indicators. The feedback also made clear that full autonomy in areas such as cloud, AI, supply chains or secure infrastructure is not realistic by 2028. What is realistic by that date is to establish the governance, mapping, funding, procurement and monitoring foundations needed to reduce high–risk dependencies and strengthen trusted European capabilities.

Finally, the discussion confirmed that the recommendations on governance, trusted information sharing and protected incident reporting should be treated as mutually reinforcing rather than separate tracks. A governance framework provides the institutional basis for cooperation; a trust–based information–sharing architecture provides the operational channel; and protected incident reporting provides one of the practical mechanisms through which information can be exchanged safely. Similarly, recommendations on skills, dual–use innovation, funding alignment, smaller Member State inclusion, strategic autonomy and monitoring should be connected through a lifecycle approach to capability development.

The prioritisation exercise showed that the first group of recommendations to be implemented should include an **EU framework for cross–sector cybersecurity governance**, a **European trust–based information–sharing architecture**, and **cybersecurity skills as a strategic EU capability priority**. This confirms that the final package should be built around three core pillars: governance, trusted exchange, and capacity.

Figure 10 Recommendation areas to be prioritised

A second prioritisation exercise highlighted **stronger European cybersecurity innovation ecosystems, hybrid-threat preparedness in EU cybersecurity policy, and an EU approach to dual-use cybersecurity innovation**. This suggests that stakeholders also see the recommendations as part of a broader resilience and competitiveness agenda. Civil-defence cyber coordination is not only a crisis-management issue; it is also connected to Europe's ability to develop, scale, and deploy cyber capabilities.

The polling on implementation challenges identified **national security and defence sensitivities and lack of trust between different actors** as the most likely barriers to progress. This confirms that the recommendations must respect national competence boundaries and the sensitivity of defence-related information, while still creating practical mechanisms for cooperation. Legal fragmentation was also identified as a barrier, but it was not the only concern. The deeper issue is the combination of legal uncertainty, institutional caution, and lack of trust.

Figure 11 Implementation Challenges

The workshop also helped identify which recommendations required the most improvement before finalisation. Several responses pointed to the recommendation on developing an **EU approach to dual-use cybersecurity innovation**, describing it as too broad, overlapping with other recommendations, or in need of greater precision. This suggests that the final version should clarify the specific added value of this recommendation. It should explain whether the focus is legal guidance, technology transfer, funding alignment, procurement, SME participation, or lifecycle governance of dual-use cyber technologies.

Participants also identified missing policy gaps. These included the need to better connect R&D results to operational use, consider post-quantum cryptography transition policy, clarify the governance and legal status of civilian cyber contributors during crises and armed conflict, and address deployable response capacity, including the EU Cybersecurity Reserve. These points helped strengthen the final recommendations by adding issues that are closely linked to preparedness, operationalisation, and future technological risk.

Figure 12 Missing Policy gaps

Finally, participants identified the recommendations on **governance, information sharing, and protected incident reporting** as the most strongly linked and therefore suitable for joint implementation. This is a key analytical result. It suggests that these recommendations should not be treated as separate policy tracks. A governance framework provides the institutional basis for cooperation; a trust-based information-sharing architecture provides the operational channel; and protected incident reporting provides one of the practical mechanisms through which information can be exchanged safely.

Overall, Workshop 4 confirmed the legitimacy and relevance of the COcyber policy recommendations, while also identifying the areas where final refinement was needed. The strongest message was that the recommendations are directionally sound, but should be made more precise, more operational, and more clearly sequenced. The final policy package should therefore emphasise implementation clusters, especially around **governance, trusted information sharing, protected reporting, skills, innovation, and hybrid-threat preparedness**.

5.2 Validation with COcyber consortium partners

A second layer of validation was carried out internally with the COcyber consortium partners: ULB, IVSZ, CCIS, and Infobalt. This internal validation process ensured that the recommendations remained consistent with the policy relevant COcyber findings that have been developed in the NEEDS Assessment, PESTEL Analysis, National Case Studies,

and their related White Papers. The validation process involved proofreading and providing feedback on each draft of the deliverable.

The consortium validation had a specific added value because partners had been directly involved in the evidence-gathering activities that informed the recommendations. Consortium partners were thus well placed to assess whether the recommendations were faithful to the evidence collected during the project and whether they reflected the diversity of national and sectoral perspectives represented in COcyber.

The internal review focused on five main questions:

- Whether the recommendations were coherent with the findings of the Needs Assessment, PESTEL analysis, and national case studies.
- Whether the thematic structure of the recommendations was complete and logically organised.
- Whether the recommendations were realistic in terms of EU and Member State competences.
- Whether the proposed implementation steps were sufficiently clear and actionable.
- Whether any recommendation required adjustment to avoid duplication, overstatement, or insufficiently supported conclusions.

At the same time, the validation process recognised a methodological limitation: some consortium partners had contributed to the underlying case studies and stakeholder consultations, meaning that their input could not be treated as entirely independent from the earlier evidence base. To address this, the internal validation was used primarily as a consistency, feasibility, and quality-assurance exercise, rather than as a substitute for external stakeholder validation. The Community workshops therefore remained the main mechanism for broader participatory validation, while the consortium review ensured internal coherence and technical soundness.

The consortium partners broadly confirmed the relevance of the proposed recommendations and supported the need for a balanced approach combining EU-level coordination with national flexibility. They also reinforced the importance of presenting the recommendations in an implementation-oriented format, including priorities, short-, medium-, and long-term steps, and possible implementation challenges. They further suggested merging similar recommendations in order to eliminate repetition and duplication.

The internal validation process therefore contributed to the final refinement of Deliverable 4.5 by ensuring that the recommendations were analytically consistent, policy-relevant, and aligned with the overall logic of the COcyber project. Combined with the Community validation workshops, the review helped transform the preliminary recommendations into

a consolidated set of policy proposals for strengthening civil–defence cybersecurity coordination, trusted information sharing, dual–use innovation, operational preparedness, and long–term European cyber resilience.

6 Final policy recommendations

The final COcyber policy recommendations respond to the growing need for a more coherent, operational and resilient European approach to cybersecurity cooperation across civilian, defence, public–sector, private–sector and research communities. Building on the project’s policy review, needs assessment, national case studies and stakeholder validation activities, the recommendations focus on areas where EU and Member State action can add practical value: clearer civil–defence coordination interfaces, trusted information sharing, protected incident reporting, skills and mobilisation, joint exercises, innovation uptake, support for smaller Member States, hybrid–threat preparedness, strategic autonomy, monitoring and common terminology. They do not propose a single institutional model for all Member States, but instead aim to strengthen interoperability, trust, legal clarity and operational readiness across diverse national systems. Together, the recommendations seek to move cybersecurity policy from broad strategic ambition toward practical implementation pathways, identifying lead actors, supporting actors, short–, medium– and long–term actions, and potential barriers that must be addressed for effective delivery.

1. Establish interoperable national civil–defence cybersecurity coordination interfaces

Priority: Very High

The EU and Member States should strengthen cross–sector cybersecurity governance by ensuring that every Member State has clear and interoperable national coordination interfaces between civilian cybersecurity authorities, defence actors, CSIRTs/CERTs, regulators, law enforcement, critical infrastructure operators, industry, academia and relevant research communities. The objective should not be to impose a single institutional model across Member States, but to ensure that national systems are operationally compatible: who acts, through which channel, under which authority, and with what safeguards during major incidents, hybrid–threat scenarios or cyber crises. This recommendation should build on NIS2, EU–CyCLONe, the Cyber Blueprint, the Cyber Solidarity Act and the EU Cyber Defence Policy. NIS2 already provides for competent authorities, single points of contact, CSIRTs and EU–CyCLONe, while the 2025 Cyber Blueprint further clarifies crisis coordination and explicitly highlights civilian–military cooperation where needed.

Lead actors: Member States, national cybersecurity authorities, defence ministries, CSIRTs/CERTs.

Supporting actors: European Commission, ENISA, EU-CyCLONe, NIS Cooperation Group, EDA where defence links are relevant.

Short term

- Member States should clarify the minimum functions of national civil–defence cybersecurity coordination interfaces, including liaison, escalation, incident routing, crisis communication, information–sharing coordination and lessons learned. These functions should be adapted to national institutional structures and tested through exercises.
- Existing NIS2 single points of contact should be connected more clearly with defence cyber actors and national crisis–management authorities during major incidents, hybrid escalation or defence–relevant cyber crises.
- EU-CyCLONe, the CSIRTs Network and Cyber Blueprint exercises should be used to test role clarity, escalation channels and coordination routines.

Medium term

- Member States should formalise and test the conditions under which defence cyber actors may support or coordinate with civilian authorities in incidents affecting critical infrastructure, hybrid–threat scenarios or national security.
- EU-funded cybersecurity projects and exercises should include civil–defence coordination criteria where operationally relevant, focusing on liaison arrangements, information–sharing thresholds, classification handling, cyber reserve activation and crisis communication.

Long term

- NIS2 peer reviews, Cyber Blueprint implementation, EU-CyCLONe activities, CSIRTs Network cooperation, Cyber Solidarity Act incident reviews and cyber exercises should feed systematically into updated coordination procedures, training scenarios, information–sharing protocols and funding priorities.

Possible Barriers to Implementation

Member States have very different institutional models, so defining “interoperable” coordination without appearing to impose a single EU model may be difficult. Defence cyber responsibilities are often linked to national security, classification and sovereignty, which may limit openness toward civilian authorities or EU-level coordination. Existing NIS2, CSIRT, EU-CyCLONe and crisis–management structures may also overlap, creating confusion over who leads during hybrid or defence–relevant incidents. A further barrier is that coordination interfaces may exist formally on paper but remain untested in real crisis conditions.

2. Reduce legal and procedural fragmentation in sensitive cyber cooperation and dual-use technology transfer

Priority: Very High

The EU should provide practical legal and procedural guidance for cybersecurity activities that sit between civilian, security and defence domains. The priority should be to help projects, SMEs, universities, public buyers and end-users understand how existing rules interact when cyber technologies move from research and pilots into lawful, trusted and operational deployment. This recommendation should not duplicate the Commission's broader dual-use R&D policy process or create a parallel legal definition of dual-use. Its added value should be a cybersecurity-specific operational pathway covering IP, access rights, classification, export controls, responsible disclosure, procurement, certification, CRA compliance, testing, deployment and misuse safeguards.

Lead actors: European Commission, Member States, ECCC.

Supporting actors: ENISA, EDA, national export-control authorities, procurement authorities, research funders, certification bodies.

Short term

- The EU should consolidate existing guidance on dual-use R&D, export controls, cybersecurity certification, procurement, responsible disclosure and operational deployment into a practical cybersecurity-specific technology-transfer pathway.
- Optional clause templates and guidance notes should complement existing Horizon Europe, Digital Europe and EDF Model Grant Agreements, helping projects manage IP, access rights, dissemination, classification, export controls, transfer to public buyers, SME participation and transition to operational deployment.
- A specialised advisory pathway should be created or designated, building on existing structures such as the European IP Helpdesk, ECCC/NCC network, national export-control authorities and cybersecurity competence centres.

Medium term

- Practical decision trees should help SMEs, universities, research organisations, public buyers and project coordinators determine whether a cyber project follows a civilian, civil-security, defence-relevant, dual-use, export-controlled or classified pathway.
- The EU should connect procurement, certification, cyber ranges, testing facilities and deployment instruments into a clear transition pathway for cyber tools with civil-defence relevance.
- A practical cyber-specific glossary should clarify how terms such as dual-use cybersecurity technology, cyber-surveillance tools, certification, research security,

responsible disclosure and operational deployment are used across funding, procurement, export control and certification frameworks.

Long term

- EU review, consultation and reporting processes should identify whether remaining cyber-specific implementation gaps can be solved through guidance, templates and advisory support, or whether targeted legal clarification is needed.
- The pathway from EU-funded cybersecurity research to operational deployment should be strengthened by connecting Horizon Europe, Digital Europe, ECCC-managed actions, EDF/EUDIS where relevant, procurement, testing, certification, export-control compliance and end-user validation.

Possible Barriers to Implementation

The biggest barrier is legal complexity: IP, export controls, classification, procurement, certification, CRA compliance and responsible disclosure are governed by different legal and administrative regimes. SMEs, universities and public buyers may lack the expertise to navigate these rules. Member States may also interpret dual-use, export-control and classification issues differently. There is a risk that guidance becomes too general to be useful, or too detailed to remain compatible with national law.

1. Build a European trust-based information-sharing architecture

Priority: Very High

The EU should support an information-sharing architecture that connects existing ISACs, CSIRTs, CERTs, sectoral cyber communities, critical infrastructure operators, cyber hubs and, where appropriate, defence-relevant stakeholders. The goal should be to make information sharing trusted, timely, protected and useful, rather than to create another platform without clear operational value. This should be anchored in NIS2 cooperation structures, the European Cybersecurity Alert System, National and Cross-Border Cyber Hubs, CSIRTs Network cooperation, ISACs and sectoral communities. The Cyber Solidarity Act already provides a framework for cyber hubs and cross-border threat detection, so the added value is to define common trust principles, shareable information categories, secure channels, anonymisation rules, controlled dissemination and feedback loops.

Lead actors: Member States, CSIRTs/CERTs, ENISA, sectoral authorities.

Supporting actors: European Commission, ECCC, ISACs, critical infrastructure operators, industry associations, defence authorities where appropriate.

Short term

- Existing EU and national mapping of ISACs, National and Cross-Border Cyber Hubs, CSIRT-linked communities and sectoral information-sharing structures should be

updated, with a focus on civil–defence, cross–sector, SME and critical–infrastructure gaps.

- A civil–defence sharing matrix should clarify which information can be shared between civilian authorities, CSIRTs, defence cyber structures, regulators, critical infrastructure operators and trusted private actors. It should cover sensitivity levels, classification handling, anonymisation, sanitisation, TLP markings, sharing thresholds, feedback obligations and conditions for defence involvement.
- Existing standards and procedures such as STIX/TAXII, MISP, TLP, CVE/CVSS and relevant EU or national classification rules should be operationalised for civil–defence scenarios, rather than promoted in abstract terms.

Medium term

- Trusted contact directories and controlled sharing channels should connect civilian authorities, defence cyber structures, critical infrastructure operators, ISACs and trusted private providers during major incidents, hybrid–threat scenarios and defence–relevant cyber crises.
- Confidentiality, classification, anonymisation and information–handling procedures should be tested in realistic scenarios to enable rapid sanitisation and controlled release of operationally useful information.
- Feedback mechanisms should ensure that SMEs, suppliers, critical infrastructure operators and reporting entities receive mitigation advice, threat context, anonymised lessons learned, sectoral alerts and links to relevant support structures.

Long term

- The EU’s emerging federated cyber–sharing architecture should be operationalised by clarifying how Cyber Hubs, CSIRTs, ISACs, EU–CyCLONe, sectoral authorities, critical infrastructure operators, trusted private providers and defence cyber structures exchange information in civil–defence and hybrid–threat scenarios.
- Outputs from information–sharing mechanisms should feed into exercise scenarios, crisis procedures, procurement requirements, capability priorities and policy guidance.

Possible Barriers to Implementation

Trust remains the central barrier. Civilian authorities, defence actors, private companies and critical infrastructure operators may be reluctant to share sensitive information if confidentiality, liability, reputational risk and classification rules are unclear. Existing platforms and communities may resist integration if they fear loss of control or duplication. Technical standards such as STIX/TAXII, MISP and TLP are useful, but unevenly

implemented. SMEs may also remain passive users if information-sharing mechanisms do not provide practical feedback or mitigation support.

2. Turn cyber incident reporting into a protected feedback and learning system

Priority: Very High

The EU should improve cyber incident reporting by making existing reporting channels more trusted, simpler and more useful. Since NIS2 and the Cyber Resilience Act already create reporting obligations, the priority should not be to add new obligations, but to reduce duplication, protect sensitive information, provide actionable feedback and use anonymised reporting data for policy learning. The text should be precise on timing: CRA reporting obligations for actively exploited vulnerabilities and severe incidents apply from 11 September 2026, and the CRA Single Reporting Platform is expected to be operational by that date.

Lead actors: Member States, CSIRTs, competent authorities.

Supporting actors: ENISA, European Commission, sectoral regulators, data-protection authorities, market-surveillance authorities.

Short term

- Reporting channels under NIS2, CRA, CER, GDPR and sectoral frameworks should be made more interoperable by clarifying routing, sequencing, reuse of submitted information and authority-to-authority coordination.
- Member States should clarify how reported incident and vulnerability information is protected, routed, anonymised, shared between authorities and, where necessary, disclosed publicly.
- The NIS2 feedback obligation should be made practical by defining what usable feedback means for SMEs, critical infrastructure operators, suppliers and public authorities. Feedback should go beyond acknowledgement and include mitigation advice, sector-specific threat context, anonymised lessons learned, relevant alerts and escalation guidance.

Medium term

- National procedures should clarify how CSIRT assistance, voluntary information sharing and supervisory enforcement are separated or coordinated in practice.
- Incident-notification templates, lessons-learned formats and alerting procedures should be harmonised across NIS2, CRA, CSIRTs, Cyber Hubs, ISACs and sectoral authorities.
- Feedback mechanisms should be monitored to ensure that reporting entities receive timely, actionable and sector-specific information.

Long term

- Aggregated and anonymised reporting data from ENISA, CIRAS, NIS2 reporting, Cyber Solidarity Act incident reviews, CSIRT inputs, Cyber Hub outputs and sectoral reporting should feed into civil–defence risk assessments, exercise scenarios, capability priorities and EU funding calls. ENISA maintains CIRAS to support Member States in submitting incident reports and publishes anonymised and aggregated incident data.
- EU and national reviews should assess whether confidentiality rules, anonymisation, liability safeguards, feedback quality and separation from enforcement are sufficient to encourage timely reporting.

Possible Barriers to Implementation

Reporting fatigue is a major risk, especially where entities already face obligations under NIS2, CRA, CER, GDPR and sectoral rules. Organisations may fear that reporting will trigger enforcement, liability, public exposure or reputational damage. Authorities may lack the capacity to provide timely, tailored feedback to reporting entities. Another barrier is interoperability between reporting channels: even if reuse of submitted information is encouraged, different authorities may still request different formats, timelines and levels of detail.

3. Make cybersecurity skills, cyber mobilisation and civil–defence training a strategic EU capability priority

Priority: High

The EU should treat cybersecurity skills as a strategic resilience capability, with specific attention to civil–defence cooperation, public–sector capacity, cyber crisis mobilisation and less–resourced Member States. This should build on the European Cybersecurity Skills Framework, the Cybersecurity Skills Academy, ENISA training, ESDC Cyber ETEE, EDA initiatives and national skills programmes. The ECSF provides a common basis for identifying cybersecurity roles, skills and competences, while the Cybersecurity Skills Academy addresses Europe’s cybersecurity skills shortage.

Lead actors: Member States, education and training authorities, and national cybersecurity authorities.

Supporting actors: European Commission, ENISA, ECCC, Cybersecurity Skills Academy, universities, vocational providers, industry, ESDC, EDA.

Short term

- The EU and Member States should identify the operational skills gaps affecting civil–defence cybersecurity coordination, including crisis liaison, classification handling, protected information sharing, incident escalation, cyber reserve

activation, critical–infrastructure coordination, SME support, cyber–hybrid preparedness and post–quantum transition.

- Integrated civil–defence training modules should connect topics that are currently often treated separately: incident reporting, classification handling, protected information sharing, PQC transition, hybrid threats, crisis escalation, defence liaison and cyber reserve activation.
- The EU Cybersecurity Reserve should be linked to national expert pools and trusted private providers by clarifying activation procedures, legal status, liability, command relationships, access rights, classification handling and post–incident accountability.

Medium term

- Member States should strengthen public–sector cyber retention for roles linked to crisis coordination, CSIRT operations, defence liaison, critical–infrastructure protection and information sharing.
- Structured secondments, exchanges and recognised role profiles should connect CSIRTs, national cyber authorities, defence cyber structures, regulators and critical infrastructure operators.
- Civil–defence training should be tested through exercises, cyber ranges and scenario–based learning rather than remaining a classroom–only activity.

Long term

- EU cyber–skills support should become more targeted toward smaller and less–resourced Member States, especially for hard–to–fill public–interest functions such as CSIRT operations, crisis coordination, defence liaison, classification handling, incident response, cyber reserve mobilisation and hybrid–threat preparedness.
- Existing preparedness communities, including ESDC Cyber ETEE, EDA cyber–defence exercises, MICNET, EU–CyCLONe, the CSIRTs Network, ENISA training, the Cyber Skills Academy and ECCC/NCC structures, should be connected into a more visible civil–defence cyber community of practice.

Possible Barriers to Implementation:

Skills shortages are already acute, especially in public–sector cyber roles, CSIRTs and less–resourced Member States. Public authorities may struggle to retain experts because private–sector salaries are more attractive. Civil–defence training also requires access to sensitive scenarios, classified procedures and trusted participants, which can limit participation. Cyber mobilisation and reserve models raise unresolved questions about liability, legal status, command relationships, access rights and post–incident accountability.

4. Institutionalise joint civilian–defence cyber exercises and operational readiness

Priority: Very High

The EU and Member States should institutionalise recurring exercises that test not only technical response, but also governance, escalation, classification, protected reporting, civilian–defence liaison, public communication, hybrid–threat response, supply–chain disruption, cyber reserve activation and recovery. This should build on Cyber Europe, EU–CyCLONe exercises such as CySOPex and BlueOLEx, CyDef–X, ESDC Cyber ETEE and national exercises. ENISA confirms that EU–CyCLONe members use CySOPex and BlueOLEx to test standard operating procedures, situational awareness and information–sharing processes.

Lead actors: Member States, ENISA, EU–CyCLONe, CSIRTs/CERTs.

Supporting actors: European Commission, EDA, critical infrastructure operators, trusted private providers, cyber ranges.

Short term

- Existing EU and national cyber exercise mapping should identify where civilian–defence participation remains insufficient.
- Scenario packages should combine issues often tested separately: critical–infrastructure disruption, supply–chain compromise, ransomware, coordinated disinformation, hybrid escalation, defence liaison, cyber reserve activation, classification handling and PQC transition risks.

Medium term

- The EU should move from separate civilian cyber–crisis and cyber–defence exercises toward a coordinated civilian–defence exercise cycle.
- Exercises should test how the Cybersecurity Emergency Mechanism and EU Cybersecurity Reserve would work in practice, including activation thresholds, procurement and contractual arrangements, trusted–provider integration, liability, access rights and coordination with national authorities.
- Cyber ranges and red–team/blue–team formats should be used for operational training where appropriate.

Long term

- Lessons learned from exercises and incident reviews should be translated into updated procedures, procurement criteria, funding priorities, training modules and operational playbooks.
- A civilian–defence cyber preparedness community of practice should connect exercise outputs, training modules, liaison procedures and lessons learned across EU and national structures.

Possible Barriers to Implementation

Joint exercises require time, funding, classified scenario design and participation from actors that do not always work together. Defence actors may be cautious about exposing operational procedures, while private operators may resist exercises that reveal vulnerabilities. Lessons learned from exercises are often not systematically translated into procurement, training or policy updates. There is also a risk of exercise overload if EU, national, sectoral and defence exercises are not coordinated into a coherent cycle.

5. Strengthen cybersecurity innovation ecosystems through procurement, certification, market access and operational demand

Priority: Medium–High

The EU should strengthen cybersecurity innovation ecosystems by connecting R&D, technology transfer, testing, certification, procurement, market access and operational demand. This recommendation should move beyond generic innovation support and focus on the last mile between promising cybersecurity solutions and actual uptake by public authorities, CSIRTs, critical infrastructure operators, SMEs and defence-relevant users. EUCC should be described accurately as a voluntary EU cybersecurity certification scheme based on Common Criteria, not as a mandatory certification requirement.

Lead actors: ECCC, European Commission, Member States, National Coordination Centres.

Supporting actors: ENISA, public buyers, industry, SMEs, universities, incubators, accelerators, certification bodies.

Short term

- Existing capability assessments, ECCC/NCC funding intelligence, ENISA NIS360, CSIRT capability work and national reviews should identify civil–defence cybersecurity capability gaps that remain insufficiently mapped.
- EU innovation–procurement guidance, CRA obligations and certification schemes such as EUCC should be translated into practical procurement guidance for cybersecurity solutions with civil–defence relevance.
- SMEs should receive targeted assistance on certification costs, CRA compliance, conformity assessment, security testing, procurement documentation, administrative burden and lifecycle support obligations.

Medium term

- ECCC/NCC, Digital Europe, European Digital Innovation Hubs, Horizon Europe, the EIC Accelerator and national ecosystem instruments should be connected more clearly to concrete end-user needs.

- Cybersecurity-specific PCP/PPI pathways should help public buyers, CSIRTs, critical infrastructure operators and defence-relevant stakeholders validate, test, certify and procure cyber solutions.
- ECCC-funded projects with civil-defence relevance should include measurable uptake plans, identified end-users, validation environments, certification or CRA-compliance pathways, procurement routes, SME participation strategies and sustainability models.

Long term

- Existing CRA, EUCC, EU cybersecurity certification, ECCC/NCC, Digital Europe, Horizon Europe and innovation-procurement instruments should reduce barriers to cross-border uptake of civil-defence cybersecurity solutions.
- Public buyers should use procurement and certification to define assurance levels, lifecycle-security requirements, trusted-provider conditions, update obligations, vulnerability-handling expectations, supply-chain transparency and dependency-risk criteria.

Possible Barriers to Implementation

The last mile from R&D to operational uptake remains difficult. Public procurement can be slow, risk-averse and administratively heavy, making it hard for SMEs to participate. Certification, CRA compliance, testing and conformity assessment may impose high costs on smaller providers. Public buyers may lack the technical expertise to define appropriate assurance levels or lifecycle-security requirements. There is also a risk that innovation funding supports pilots without a credible procurement or deployment pathway.

6. Ensure smaller and less-resourced Member States benefit from EU cyber scaling

Priority: High

EU cybersecurity policy should explicitly support smaller Member States and less mature ecosystems so that EU-level scaling reduces capability gaps rather than reinforcing them. This should include access to shared services, Cyber Hubs, testing facilities, funding support, skills programmes, procurement guidance, technical assistance, cyber ranges and trusted-provider support.

Lead actors: European Commission, ECCC, Member States.

Supporting actors: NCCs, ENISA, Cybersecurity Reserve providers, larger Member State authorities, regional ecosystems.

Short term

- Existing ECCC/NCC, ENISA, Digital Europe, Cybersecurity Skills Academy and national ecosystem assessments should identify the practical barriers affecting smaller and less-resourced Member States.
- Technical-assistance services should focus on consortium-building, proposal preparation, partner search, administrative simplification, co-financing barriers, dual-use considerations, certification and procurement pathways.
- Smaller Member States should participate meaningfully, not only formally, in ECCC/NCC cooperation, NIS2 peer learning and Cyber Hub activities.

Medium term

- Smaller ecosystems should have practical access to National and Cross-Border Cyber Hubs, SOC-related capabilities, EDA/PESCO cyber ranges where relevant, ECCC-funded testing facilities, CSIRT and ISAC threat-intelligence mechanisms and the EU Cybersecurity Reserve.
- Structured mentoring or twinning arrangements should connect more mature and less mature civil-defence cybersecurity ecosystems.
- Cyber Hubs and the Cybersecurity Reserve should be used to provide deployable support during major incidents, while also generating lessons for preparedness and capacity building.

Long term

- EU and national funding mechanisms should monitor and mitigate concentration risks in cybersecurity funding, expertise and capability development.
- Smaller and less-resourced Member States should be supported in developing niche areas of civil-defence cybersecurity excellence, such as CSIRT maturity, cyber ranges, secure communications, critical-infrastructure resilience, cyber reserve models, threat-intelligence sharing, PQC transition, SME innovation, certification support or hybrid-threat preparedness.

Possible Barriers to Implementation

Smaller Member States may lack the administrative capacity to access EU funding, join complex consortia or participate meaningfully in EU-level structures. Co-financing requirements, certification costs, procurement procedures and staff shortages may limit their ability to benefit from available instruments. More mature Member States and larger organisations may capture a disproportionate share of funding and expertise. Twinning, mentoring and shared services can help, but they require sustained coordination and political willingness from both stronger and weaker ecosystems.

7. Integrate hybrid-threat preparedness and post-quantum transition into cybersecurity policy

Priority: Medium-High

The EU should integrate cybersecurity more explicitly with hybrid-threat preparedness, crisis management, strategic communication, foreign interference response, economic security, supply-chain resilience and post-quantum cryptography. Cyber incidents increasingly interact with disinformation, sabotage, coercion, dependency exploitation and geopolitical escalation. The recommendation should therefore connect cybersecurity to the EU Hybrid Toolbox, FIMI Toolbox, Cyber Diplomacy Toolbox, Preparedness Union Strategy, Cyber Blueprint and PQC roadmap. The PQC wording should remain cautious: the Commission issued a 2024 Recommendation encouraging Member States to develop coordinated PQC strategies, followed by a 2025 coordinated implementation roadmap for transition.

Lead actors: Member States, European Commission, EEAS, ENISA, national cybersecurity and crisis-management authorities.

Supporting actors: defence ministries, law enforcement, strategic communication bodies, EDA, critical infrastructure operators.

Short term

- Cyber-crisis, hybrid-threat and sectoral exercise scenarios should be integrated into civil-defence risk assessment and preparedness.
- Member States should translate PQC roadmap milestones into migration inventories, risk prioritisation, procurement requirements, testing plans, funding needs and exercise scenarios for public-sector systems, critical infrastructure and defence-relevant networks.
- Civil-defence cyber exercises should test links between cyber incident response, strategic communication, FIMI analysis, diplomatic response, attribution-sensitive messaging and defence liaison.

Medium term

- EU hybrid-threat, cyber-crisis, critical-entity resilience and FIMI procedures should be tested for combined cyber scenarios involving disinformation, supply-chain disruption, economic coercion or physical sabotage.
- Lessons from Member States highly exposed to hybrid threats should be translated into practical civil-defence guidance, including operational playbooks, escalation thresholds, strategic communication procedures and information-sharing rules.

Long term

- The EU cyber-hybrid resilience framework should connect the Cyber Blueprint, Cyber Solidarity Act, EU Hybrid Toolbox, FIMI Toolbox, Cyber Diplomacy Toolbox,

CER Directive, Preparedness Union Strategy and national crisis-management structures into tested civil-defence playbooks.

- PQC transition, dependency mapping and ICT supply-chain assurance should be integrated into procurement criteria, supplier-risk assessments, testing requirements, funding priorities and exercise scenarios.

Possible Barriers to Implementation

Hybrid-threat preparedness cuts across cyber, defence, diplomacy, crisis management, strategic communication, law enforcement and critical infrastructure protection, making institutional ownership difficult. PQC transition is technically complex, expensive and long-term; many organisations may not yet have inventories of cryptographic assets or migration plans. Combined cyber-hybrid exercises may be politically sensitive because they involve attribution, foreign interference, disinformation and defence escalation. There is also a risk that hybrid-threat language becomes too broad unless linked to concrete playbooks and operational thresholds.

8. Align EU cyber funding instruments around capability development and strategic autonomy

Priority: High

The EU should align cybersecurity funding instruments around a full capability lifecycle: needs identification, research, testing, validation, certification, procurement, deployment, training, maintenance and policy learning. This should include Horizon Europe, Digital Europe, ECCC-managed actions, EDF/EUDIS where appropriate, EDA-linked mechanisms, national funding and procurement instruments. The ECCC's role should be framed accurately as strengthening Europe's cybersecurity capacities and competitiveness through cooperation with the Network of National Coordination Centres. The recommendation should operationalise strategic autonomy through dependency mapping, trusted procurement requirements, certification, secure cloud and infrastructure choices, supply-chain assurance and investment priorities, while preserving cooperation with trusted international partners.

Lead actors: European Commission, ECCC, Member States.

Supporting actors: EDA, EDF/EUDIS structures, NCCs, ENISA, public buyers, industry, SMEs.

Short term

- A practical cyber capability pathway guide should show how civil-defence cyber projects can move from research to validation, procurement, deployment and sustainability.

- EU and national mapping should identify where projects still fail to progress from research to testing, certification, procurement, operational deployment and long-term maintenance.
- EU-funded cybersecurity projects with civil-defence relevance should include credible exploitation, procurement, certification, CRA-compliance, maintenance and post-project sustainability plans.

Medium term

- Selected cybersecurity calls across Horizon Europe, Digital Europe, ECCC-managed actions and EDF/EUDIS should be better aligned where legally possible and operationally useful.
- Matchmaking should be more targeted toward concrete civil-defence capability needs, linking SMEs, research actors, CSIRTs, public authorities, critical infrastructure operators, defence-relevant stakeholders and trusted providers.
- Funding should prioritise implementation gaps in dependency mapping, PQC transition, secure infrastructure, trusted European capabilities, cyber ranges, secure communications, threat intelligence and critical-infrastructure resilience.

Long term

- The EU should strengthen continuity between research, validation, testing, certification, procurement, deployment, training, maintenance and lessons learned.
- Successful civil-defence cybersecurity pilots should be scaled across Member States through reusable procurement specifications, shared service models, common assurance requirements, certification pathways, SME scaling support and deployment packages.
- EU funding should apply a de-risking, not decoupling logic by prioritising high-risk dependency areas while preserving cooperation with trusted international partners where it strengthens resilience and interoperability.

Possible Barriers to Implementation

EU funding instruments have different legal bases, objectives, eligibility rules and timelines, which makes alignment difficult. Horizon Europe, Digital Europe, ECCC-managed actions, EDF/EUDIS and national procurement do not always follow the same logic. Projects may still end after research or pilot stages without funding for testing, certification, procurement, deployment and maintenance. Strategic autonomy can also be politically sensitive if it is interpreted as protectionism or decoupling rather than risk-based dependency reduction.

9. Embed monitoring, peer review and policy learning across EU cybersecurity initiatives

Priority: Medium

Major EU-supported cybersecurity initiatives should include monitoring, peer review and lessons-learned mechanisms. This is especially important for governance, information sharing, incident reporting, dual-use innovation, funding, skills, cyber reserve models, smaller Member State support and hybrid-threat preparedness. This recommendation should build on ENISA reporting, NIS2 peer reviews, NIS360, Cyber Solidarity Act incident reviews, EU-CyCLONe activities, ECCC programme monitoring and cyber exercises. ENISA's NIS360 assesses the maturity and criticality of NIS2 sectors and provides a useful basis for policy learning.

Lead actors: European Commission, ENISA, ECCC, Member States.

Supporting actors: EU-CyCLONe, NIS Cooperation Group, NCCs, CSIRTs, sectoral authorities, project coordinators.

Short term

- A targeted set of civil-defence cybersecurity implementation indicators should measure gaps not yet consistently captured, including governance interoperability, quality of information-sharing feedback, usability of reporting channels for SMEs, defence liaison arrangements, cyber reserve readiness, classification-handling capacity, exercise-based readiness and uptake of civil-defence capabilities.
- EU-funded cybersecurity projects with civil-defence relevance should show how lessons learned will be captured, shared and implemented in operational practice.
- NIS2 peer-review methodologies, ENISA assessment tools and EU cybersecurity certification peer-review practices should be adapted to include a civil-defence dimension.

Medium term

- NIS2 voluntary peer reviews should assess how national cybersecurity authorities, CSIRTs, crisis-management bodies, defence cyber structures, regulators, critical infrastructure authorities and private-sector contact points cooperate during major incidents and hybrid-threat scenarios.
- A civil-defence cybersecurity benchmarking layer should enable policy learning while protecting sensitive national, defence and operational information.
- Monitoring outputs should feed into EU guidance, funding calls, procurement priorities, exercise scenarios and national implementation support.

Long term

- The EU should institutionalise a continuous cybersecurity policy-learning cycle. Evidence from ENISA reporting, NIS2 peer reviews, Cyber Solidarity Act incident reviews, Cyber Blueprint implementation, EU-CyCLONE activities, cyber exercises and EU-funded project outcomes should be translated into updated civil-defence coordination procedures, funding calls, procurement requirements, training modules, information-sharing rules and operational playbooks.

Possible Barriers to Implementation

Monitoring and peer review may be resisted if Member States fear exposure of sensitive national weaknesses, especially in defence-relevant areas. Indicators may be difficult to define without oversimplifying complex governance, trust and readiness issues. Data collection could become burdensome for project coordinators, CSIRTs and national authorities. There is also a risk that lessons-learned processes remain descriptive and are not connected to concrete changes in funding calls, operational procedures, training modules or procurement requirements.

10. Develop a common EU cyber-defence terminology and doctrine framework

Priority: Medium

The EU and Member States should develop a common cyber-defence terminology and doctrine framework to support interoperability, shared understanding and practical implementation across civilian, defence, public-sector, private-sector and research communities. The EU already has a wide range of cybersecurity and cyber-defence policies, strategies and legal instruments, but it still lacks a sufficiently common operational vocabulary explaining how key concepts, roles, procedures and escalation mechanisms should be understood across Member States. This recommendation should not aim to impose a single language, doctrine or centralised EU command model. Instead, it should establish a common conceptual and procedural framework that can be translated consistently across Member States and applied in national contexts. It should draw lessons from NATO's doctrinal and terminology approach where relevant, while preserving EU autonomy of decision-making and respecting the EU's distinct legal and institutional framework.

Lead actors: Member States, EEAS, EUMS, European Commission, Council, EDA.

Supporting actors: ENISA, EU-CyCLONE, CSIRTs Network, NIS Cooperation Group, ECCC, national cybersecurity authorities, defence ministries, industry, academia, standardisation bodies and critical infrastructure operators.

Short term

- The EU should map terminology across NIS2, the Cyber Solidarity Act, the Cyber Resilience Act, the EU Cyber Defence Policy, the Cyber Blueprint, EU-CyCLONE, ENISA guidance, EDA activities and national cyber strategies.

- A first EU civil–defence cyber glossary should cover priority terms such as cyber defence, cyber crisis, major incident, escalation, cyber reserve, protected reporting, trusted information sharing, dual–use cybersecurity technology, operational readiness, hybrid threat and strategic autonomy.
- The glossary should be translated and validated across Member States to support consistent understanding in national administrative and operational contexts.
- EU terminology should be compared with NATO AJP–3.20 and NATOTerm where relevant, while avoiding automatic duplication where EU legal or institutional concepts differ.

Medium term

- Doctrine–like EU guidance should explain how civil–defence cyber cooperation should work in practice, including roles, escalation routes, information–sharing thresholds, classification handling, sanitisation procedures, feedback loops and links between civilian and defence actors.
- EU–supported exercises should test whether the terminology and procedures are understood consistently.
- The terminology should be integrated into EU–funded cybersecurity projects, training modules, cyber ranges, procurement guidance, incident–reporting templates and capability–development programmes.
- Sector–specific annexes may be needed for critical infrastructure, defence, cloud, AI–enabled cyber tools, PQC, cyber reserves and dual–use cybersecurity innovation.

Long term

- A mature EU cyber–defence doctrine framework should translate EU policies and strategies into shared operational concepts and procedures.
- The framework should support interoperability between national cyber authorities, defence actors, CSIRTs, EU–CyCLONE, MICNET, critical infrastructure operators and trusted private providers.
- It should be periodically updated through lessons learned from exercises, major incidents, peer reviews, Cyber Solidarity Act incident reviews and evolving NATO doctrine where relevant.

Possible Barriers to Implementation

Terminology is politically and institutionally sensitive because concepts such as cyber defence, cyber crisis, escalation, strategic autonomy and hybrid threat may be understood differently across Member States. Defence doctrine remains closely linked to national sovereignty and, for many Member States, NATO frameworks. The EU will need to

avoid duplicating NATO terminology while still developing concepts suited to its own legal and institutional framework. Translation across languages and administrative cultures may also create inconsistencies unless the terminology is tested in exercises and operational guidance.

7 Conclusions

This deliverable has developed the final COcyber policy recommendations for strengthening coordination between civilian and defence cybersecurity communities in Europe. The analysis confirms that the EU already possesses a substantial and evolving cybersecurity policy framework, including legislation, crisis-management mechanisms, cyber-defence initiatives, funding instruments, certification tools and operational cooperation structures. However, the main challenge is no longer only the absence of policy. It is the difficulty of translating this increasingly dense policy landscape into practical, trusted and interoperable cooperation across different institutional communities, Member States, sectors and levels of governance.

The findings of the deliverable show that civilian-defence cybersecurity coordination is becoming a core requirement of European resilience. Civilian infrastructures, defence preparedness, public authorities, private operators, research organisations, SMEs and critical technology providers increasingly depend on shared digital systems, suppliers, skills and data flows. Cyber incidents affecting energy, transport, telecommunications, cloud services, public administration, health systems, supply chains or space-based services can quickly become relevant not only for civilian continuity, but also for defence readiness, crisis management and hybrid-threat response. This interdependence requires more structured cooperation before crises occur, rather than improvised coordination during major incidents.

The recommendations should therefore not be read as a flat list of equally urgent actions. They form a sequenced implementation agenda. The **very high priority** actions should come first because they create the operational foundation for all other measures. These are establishing interoperable national civil-defence cybersecurity coordination interfaces, building a European trust-based information-sharing architecture, turning cyber incident reporting into a protected feedback and learning system, and institutionalising joint civilian-defence cyber exercises and operational readiness. These four priorities address the most immediate implementation gaps, namely unclear roles, weak trust, fragmented reporting, untested procedures and insufficient operational coordination during cyber crises.

The next layer of action consists of **high priority** recommendations that enable and sustain this operational foundation. These include making cybersecurity skills, cyber

mobilisation and civil–defence training a strategic EU capability priority, ensuring that smaller and less–resourced Member States benefit from EU cyber scaling, and aligning EU cyber funding instruments around capability development and strategic autonomy. These recommendations are essential because coordination mechanisms cannot function without skilled personnel, balanced capacity across Member States, and funding pathways that support deployment, maintenance and long–term capability development rather than isolated pilots.

A further set of **medium–high priority** recommendations should support implementation by reducing legal, technical and market barriers. These include reducing legal and procedural fragmentation in sensitive cyber cooperation and dual–use technology transfer, strengthening cybersecurity innovation ecosystems through procurement, certification, market access and operational demand, and integrating hybrid–threat preparedness and post–quantum transition into cybersecurity policy. These issues are strategically important, but they require careful sequencing because they involve complex legal frameworks, technical transitions, procurement practices and institutional responsibilities.

Finally, the medium priority recommendations on monitoring, peer review, policy learning, and common EU cyber–defence terminology should be treated as long–term enablers. They are important for coherence, interoperability and continuous improvement, but they should support implementation rather than delay it. Monitoring and peer review should help identify what works in practice, while common terminology and doctrine–like guidance should gradually improve shared understanding across civilian, defence, public–sector, private–sector and research communities.

The validation process carried out through COcyber policy–oriented workshops and consortium engagement confirmed the relevance of the recommendations while also highlighting the need for realism, sequencing and implementation detail. Stakeholders supported the overall direction of the policy package but stressed that recommendations must identify clearer lead actors, realistic timelines, safeguards for sensitive information, and practical mechanisms that can be used by smaller Member States, SMEs and less mature ecosystems. This feedback helped refine the final recommendations towards a more actionable and prioritised implementation pathway. The next step will be to adapt this deliverable into a shorter and more targeted COcyber Policy Recommendation White Paper in June. The White Paper should place particular emphasis on the highest–priority actions and present them as the immediate implementation agenda for EU and national policymakers. It should clearly distinguish between actions that need to be launched first, supporting measures that build capacity and funding alignment, and longer–term enablers that improve coherence, monitoring and policy learning.

Overall, Deliverable D4.5 contributes to the broader European effort to move from fragmented cybersecurity coordination towards a more integrated model of preparedness. Its main message is that effective civilian–defence cybersecurity

cooperation depends not only on strategies and legal instruments, but on trusted operational interfaces, shared procedures, protected reporting channels, tested exercises, sustained capabilities and continuous learning. By prioritising the most urgent and foundational actions first, COcyber provides a practical basis for strengthening Europe's ability to prevent, prepare for, respond to and learn from cyber incidents that cut across civilian and defence domains.

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8. Annex

COcyber Policy-Oriented workshop: Validating Europe's current Civilian-Defence Cybersecurity policy Landscape

Agenda

11:00 – 11:05 Welcome & framing

- COcyber project context
- Objectives of the Workshop

11:05 – 11:15 Key findings from the policy & literature review

- Presentation of the Policy and Literature Review findings

11:15 – 11:35 Interactive validation breakouts

Participants split into **3 moderated breakout groups**, each addressing:

- What is **accurate and robust** in the review?
- What is **missing, overstated, or unclear**?
- Which **3 gaps** most urgently require policy action?

11:35 – 11:50 Feedback

- Moderators present findings from breakout rooms
- Mentimeter to collect feedback:
 - most critical gaps

11:50 – 12:00 Next steps & closing

- How validation input will feed into draft policy recommendations
- Timeline and invitation to **Workshop #2**

COcyber Policy–Oriented workshop: Integration of COcyber Case study Findings

Agenda

11:00 – 11:10 Welcome & framing

- Objectives of the Workshop
- COcyber project context

11:10 – 11:25 Key findings from the policy & literature review

- Presentation of the case study findings and their policy relevant conclusions

11:25 – 11:40 Interactive validation breakouts

Participants split into **3 moderated breakout groups**, each addressing:

Validation

- What findings are robust and accurate?

Gaps & Blind Spots

- What is missing, overstated, or insufficiently evidenced?

Policy Integration

- Which 3 findings require urgent EU-level policy attention?
- What would improve civilian–defence integration in practice?

11:40 – 11:50 Feedback

- Moderators present findings from breakout rooms
- Mentimeter to collect feedback:

11:50 – 12:00 Next steps & closing

- How validation input will feed into draft policy recommendations
- Timeline and invitation to **Workshop #3**

COcyber Policy–Oriented workshop: Preliminary Policy Recommendations

Agenda

11:00 – 11:10 Welcome & framing

- Objectives of the Workshop

- COcyber project context

11:10 – 11:25 Key findings from the policy & literature review

- Presentation of the Preliminary Policy recommendations

11:25 – 11:40 Interactive validation breakouts

Participants split into **3 moderated breakout groups**, each addressing:

Robustness & Accuracy

- Do the recommendations reflect policy and operational realities?
- Are assumptions evidence-based?

Gaps & Feasibility

- What is missing, unclear, or impractical?
- What barriers to implementation are underestimated?

Prioritisation

- Which 3 recommendations require urgent EU-level action?
- Which could realistically be implemented within 2–3 years?

11:40 – 11:50 Feedback

- Moderators present findings from breakout rooms
- Mentimeter to collect feedback:

11:50 – 12:00 Next steps & closing

- How validation input will feed into draft policy recommendations
- Timeline and invitation to **the final Policy workshop**

COcyber Policy-Oriented workshop: Final Policy Recommendations

Agenda

10:00 – 10:30 | Arrival & Networking Coffee (On-site)

Online participants admitted and technical check.

10:30 – 10:50 | Welcome & Strategic Framing

- Welcome and short presentation on the project – **COcyber Coordinator Alessandra Zini**
- Recap of validation journey – **Organiser Kristian Reeson**

- Literature & policy review
- Case study integration
- Preliminary recommendations workshop
- Objectives of the day

10:50 – 11:05 Keynote Speech

Lars Koreman EEAS

11:05 – 11:35 | Presentation: Final COcyber Policy Recommendations

Final Recommendations

- Governance & institutional alignment
- Operational coordination mechanisms
- Funding & capability development
- Sovereignty & infrastructure considerations
- Implementation roadmap (short-, medium-, long-term)

11:35 – 11:40 | Clarification Q&A (Plenary)

Structured Q&A to clarify scope and assumptions before validation.

11:40 – 12:10 | Thematic Breakout Validation Sessions (Round 1)

Participants divided into **4 thematic groups** (hybrid-enabled):

1. **Governance & Institutional Coordination – Kristian Reeson**
2. **Operational Cooperation & Information Sharing – Manuel Shaeken**
3. **Capability Development & Funding Alignment – Dr Marios Thoma**
4. **Strategic Autonomy & Sovereignty Dimensions – Elena Wetter**

Each group assesses:

- Are recommendations realistic?
- What implementation barriers exist?
- What must be clarified or refined?
- What indicators could measure success?

Moderators capture:

- Validation points
- Required refinements
- Implementation enablers

- Risk factors

12:10 – 12:30 | Plenary Reporting & Synthesis

Each group:

- 3–5 minutes presentation
- 1–2 minutes Q&A

12:30 – 13:30 | Lunch Break

13:30 – 14:00 | Thematic Breakout Sessions (Round 2 – Prioritisation & Implementation)

Same groups refine:

- Top 3 priority actions (2026–2028)
- Quick wins (within 12–18 months)
- Long-term structural reforms
- Key actors responsible (EU, MS, Agencies, Industry)
- Dependencies and risks

Outputs prepared on structured templates.

14:00 – 14:20 | Plenary Reporting & Synthesis

Each group:

- 3–5 minutes presentation
- 1–2 minutes Q&A

14:20 – 14:35 | Coffee and networking Break

14:35 – 14:50 | Mentimeter Validation & Stakeholder Endorsement

Live polling:

- Overall robustness of policy package (1–5)
- Most urgent recommendation
- Most feasible short-term action
- Recommendation requiring further refinement
- Willingness to support dissemination/implementation

Visual results discussed live.

14:50 – 15:00 | Implementation Pathway & Next Steps

- Integration of feedback

- Finalisation timeline
- Dissemination strategy (EU institutions, MS, agencies)
- Potential follow-up policy dialogue formats
- Sustainability beyond project lifetime